

Thermal Design Study of the Electrical Cabling System of Cryogenic Payloads in the Einstein Telescope

Bachelor Thesis of

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Bachelor thesis

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THERMAL DESIGN STUDY OF THE ELECTRICAL CABLING SYSTEM OF CRYOGENIC PAYLOADS IN THE EINSTEIN TELESCOPE

THERMISCHE AUSLEGUNGSSTUDIE DES ELEKTRISCHEN KABELSYSTEMS FÜR KRYOGENE PAYLOADS IM EINSTEIN TELESKOP

Background:

The Einstein Telescope (ET) is a third-generation gravitational-wave detector planned in Europe. Its low-frequency interferometer (ET-LF) requires cryogenic mirror temperatures to reduce the thermal noise that limits the sensitivity in its most important frequency band of 3 Hz to 10 Hz. These mirrors represent the core optics in so-called cryogenic payloads, which are suspended from super-attenuators within large vacuum towers and cryostats, respectively.

For interferometer alignment procedures, system control and detector operation, various instrumentation equipment is required on a payload within a cryostat. Most of the electrical cabling is inserted alongside the main payload suspension system from above into the cryostat, inducing a parasitic heat load due to the direct connection between the room-temperature part and the cryogenic payload. Within the scope of this thesis, the thermal design of an ET-LF payload cabling system shall be studied, based on existing designs currently used in the Advanced Virgo detector (AdVirgo) in Italy and in the Japanese KAGRA detector. These designs need to be adapted to the requirements and operating conditions in ET.

Scope of work:

The Bachelor's thesis shall include the following main work packages:

- Familiarisation with ET-LF cryostat design and existing electrical cabling systems
- Literature study on electrical cabling used in cryogenics relevant for the application
- Design proposal for electrical cabling system adequate for the ET-LF payloads
- Calculation of parasitic heat load into the cryostat via the electrical cabling

The Bachelor's thesis shall be conducted at TTK-KKT (KIT Campus South). It shall be written in English language. The results shall be presented in the ITTK Institute seminar.

The rules for safeguarding good scientific practice at KIT shall be applied.

Start of work: 28.10.2024

Supervisor: Xhesika Korovesi, M.Sc.

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Steffen Grohmann

I hereby declare that I have written this thesis independently, that I have not used any sources or aids other than those indicated , and that I have marked as such any passages/thoughts taken directly or indirectly from external sources. I furthermore declare that I have complied with the current version of the Statutes for Safeguarding Good Research Practice at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT).

Karlsruhe, 14.03.2025

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(Defne Çelik)

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Contents

Lists of symbols and abbreviations	vii
1 Introduction	1
2 Theoretical background	3
2.1 Electrical cables and wires	3
2.2 Wire material properties	4
2.3 Thermal analysis of electrical wires	6
3 State of the art: Gravitational Wave Detectors	10
3.1 Gravitational Wave Detector Payloads	12
3.1.1 Payload Instrumentation	12
3.2 Advanced Virgo Plus (AdV+)	15
3.2.1 Room-temperature Payload of AdV+	16
3.3 KAGRA Interferometer	21
3.3.1 Cryogenic Payload of KAGRA	21
3.4 The Einstein Telescope (ET)	25
3.4.1 Cryogenic Payload in the low-frequency interferometer of ET	26
4 Optimization of electrical wiring for cryogenic applications	31
4.1 Optimization methodology	31
4.2 Electrical wiring for the GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat	36
4.2.1 GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat	36
4.2.2 Optimization	38
5 Optimization of electrical wiring for the ET	43
5.1 System definition and input parameters	43
5.2 Cooling Concepts and Thermal Analysis Cases	46
5.3 Evaluation of the Thermal Analysis Cases	47
5.4 Wire material selection	51
5.4.1 Material selection approach	51
5.4.2 Wire material variation	53
5.5 Design Proposal	56
6 Summary and Outlook	61
Bibliography	63
A Appendix	71

List of Figures

2.1	Schematic representation of an electrical cable, highlighting its main parts	3
2.2	Thermal conductivity of various materials as a function of temperature [1]	5
2.3	Scheme of a conduction cooled electrical wire	6
3.1	Schematic representation of a typical interferometer configuration. [2]	10
3.2	Schematic representation of the payload structure including platform, marionette, test mass and reaction mass	11
3.3	Classification of general electrical instruments used in a payload. . . .	12
3.4	3D images of an SA tower (a) and the Filter 7 (b) of AdV+ [3]	15
3.5	CAD drawing of the assembled payload in AdV+. The drawing includes actuator cage excluded mounts for components located around the mirror, cage components and their mounts (ring heater, baffles, actuators), marionette and its components [4]	16
3.6	Actuation scheme of the AdV+ (a) and image of mirror-compensation plate configuration (b) [5]	18
3.7	Schematic representation of AdV+ payload, illustrating the main structural components and key instrumentation, including displacement measurement, position adjustment and thermal compensation elements.	20
3.8	The images of the cables used between filter 4 and platform (filter 7), (left: before installation, right: after installation into the conductance pipe and mounting on filter 7 (platform)) [3].	20
3.9	The schematic of KAGRA Type-A suspension tower showing the arrangement of the room-temperature SA and cryogenic payload, including the thermal shields (80 K and 8 K) [6] (a) and the cryogenic Payload of KAGRA (b) [7]	22
3.10	Image of the new moving mass system used in the platform and the marionette [8]	23
3.11	The schematics of suggested displacement sensors for the KAGRA Payload: reflective photo sensor (a) [8] and OSEM from two different view points [9] (b)	23
3.12	Schematic representation of KAGRA payload, illustrating the main structural components and key instrumentation (Information on the temperature of platform and marionette is not available).	24
3.13	Interferometer configuration of ET, highlighting the xylophone design [10]	26

3.14	Scheme of the SA (a) [11] with the payload housed in the cryostat (b) [12]	27
3.15	Baseline design of the cryogenic payload of ET, including platform, marionette, test mass (mirror) and actuator cage [13]	27
3.16	Schematic of the ET-LF cryogenic payload design proposal for electrical instruments, including buffer elements and main components.	28
4.1	Flowchart of the optimization algorithm	33
4.2	The schematic of the Cernox wiring and feedthroughs with thermalization stages (a) and the schematic of GRAVITHELIUM test cryostat (b) <i>courtesy of X. Korovesi and M. Stamm</i>	38
4.3	Heat load distribution across all inputs for optimized values. The left chart represents tshows the distirbution from 300 K to 60 K, while the right chart from 60 K to 5 K.	41
5.1	Schematic representation of the distances between the cryostat and payload components, illustrating the thermalization stages at 80 K and 5 K.	44
5.2	Heat load distribution for different cases, divided among wire thermalization at 80 K, 5 K (if present) and the payload.	49
5.3	Electrical resistivity of different materials as a function of temperature (Diagram plotted with material properties from [14])	52
5.4	Thermal conductivity of different materials as a function of temperature (Diagram plotted with material properties from [14]))	52

List of Tables

3.1	Electrical wire connections of Filter 7 (platform) [15].	17
3.2	Electrical wire connections of the marionette [15]	17
3.3	Electrical wire connections of a ring heater (RH), compensation plate (CP) and the coils of the mirror [15]	18
3.4	Overview of instruments in the payload of AdV+, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management)	19
3.5	Overview of instruments in the payload of KAGRA, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, intermediate mass, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management).	25
3.6	Overview of instruments in the proposed ET-LF cryogenic payload design, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management). Items denoted by * are buffer instruments.	28
4.1	Dimension and properties of an exemplary wire	34
4.2	Results of the exemplary wire without an optimization	34
4.3	Results of wire diameter variation	35
4.4	Results of wire length variation	36
4.5	Comparison of results for the initial design and optimized design (first row: initial design, second row: optimized design)	36
4.6	Input parameters for the electrical wiring of GRAVITHELIUM instruments.	38
4.7	Input results showing cold end heat loads.	39
4.8	Optimized results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the first temperature range.	40
4.9	Optimized results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the second temperature range.	40
4.10	Achievable results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the first temperature range.	42
4.11	Achievable results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the second temperature range.	42
5.1	Input parameters for electrical wiring of payload instruments (All wires are made of copper (RRR = 50), except the phosphor bronze Cernox wires. Buffer instruments are denoted with *).	45

5.2	Overview of the six thermal analysis cases for the electrical wires with different payload cooling concepts and wire thermalization strategies.	46
5.3	Comparison of total heat loads for Monolithic Cooling (Cases 1-3)	47
5.4	Comparison of total heat loads for Helium Cooling (Cases 4-6)	48
5.5	The parasitic heat load reduction rates from \dot{Q}_c Input to \dot{Q}_c Achievable for each case	50
5.6	Overview of the 14 material selection cases with different current levels and thermal paths.	53
5.7	The two best-performing materials for each of the 14 material selection cases from Table 5.6, ranked from lowest to highest parasitic heat load (\dot{Q}_c).	54
5.8	Overview of the selected materials for each case from Table 5.6. Case 12 denotes the exception for coil wires with *.	56
5.9	Overview of the total parasitic heat load values of the proposed electrical wiring design	57
5.10	Design proposal for electrical wiring between 300 K and 80 K.	58
5.11	Design proposal for electrical wiring between 80 K and 5 K.	59
5.12	Design proposal for electrical wiring between 5 K and payload	60
A.1	Comparison of instruments of payloads of AdV+ and KAGRA, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, intermediate mass, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal compensation). Instruments that either do not exist or could not be identified using publicly available information are denoted with –.	72
A.2	Optimized heat load results for Case 1: 300 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling	73
A.3	Optimized heat load results for Case 2: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling	74
A.4	Optimized heat load results for Case 3: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling	75
A.5	Optimized heat load results for Case 4: 300 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling	76
A.6	Optimized heat load results for Case 5: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling	77
A.7	Optimized heat load results for Case 6: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling	78
A.8	Optimized heat load results for the intermediate thermalization stage at 80 K	79
A.9	Optimized heat load results for the intermediate thermalization stage at 5 K	80

Lists of symbols and abbreviations

List of Abbreviations

AdVirgo	Advanced Virgo
AdV+	Advanced Virgo Plus
ET	Einstein Telescope
ET-LF	Low-frequency Interferometer of ET
ET-HF	High-frequency Interferometer of ET
LIGO	Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory
SA	Superattenuator
LVDT	Linear Variable Differential Transformer
HWS	Hartmann Wave-Front Sensors
RRR	Residual Resistivity Ratio
OFHC	Oxygen Free High Conductivity
AWG	American Wire Gauge
GAS	Geometric Anti-Spring
OSEM	Optical Sensor and Electromagnetic Actuator
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
HLVIS	Heat Link Vibraton Isolation Systems
NbTi	Niobium-Titanium Alloy
GR	GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat

List of Symbols

Symbol	Unit	Description
$\lambda(T)$	$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	Thermal conductivity
$\rho(T)$	$\Omega \text{ m}$	Electrical resistivity
$R(T)$	Ω	Electrical resistance
A	m^2	Cross section area
d	m	Diameter
d_0	mm	Input diameter
d_{\min}	mm	Minimum allowable diameter
L	m	Length
L_0	mm	Input length
L_{\max}	m	Maximum allowable length
I	A	Current
I_0	mA	Input current
I_{opt}	A	Optimal current
I_{\max}	A	Ampacity limit
T_c	K	Cold end temperature
T_h	K	Warm end temperature
\dot{Q}_λ	W	Heat load due to thermal conduction
\dot{Q}_I	W	Heat load due to Joule heat
$\dot{Q}_{I,\max}$	W m^{-3}	Maximum allowed volumetric Joule heat
$\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$	W	Overall Joule heat
\dot{Q}_h	W	Heat load on the warm end of a wire
\dot{Q}_c	W	Heat load on the cold end of a wire
$\dot{Q}_{c,\min}$	W	Theoretical minimum value of heat load on the cold end of a wire

1. Introduction

Gravitational wave astronomy has undergone significant advancements in recent years, providing unique insights into the universe, such as the detection of black hole formations and neutron star coalescences [16]. Decades of research on highly sensitive detectors was invested, which led the construction of the Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO) and VIRGO, which enabled the first detection of gravitational waves in 2015 [17].

Gravitational wave detectors are based on laser interferometry to detect gravitational waves. The detectors consist of long perpendicular arms, where laser beams are reflected between the mirrors. A change in the interference pattern of the laser beams indicates the presence of a gravitational wave. Since these detections are highly sensitive, isolation from external noise is essential to maintain the stability of the mirror. To mitigate one of the primary noise sources, the seismic noise, detectors include Superattenuator (SA) systems, progressively suspending the core element, the mirror, with multiple stages. The lowest stages of SA is the payload, a multi-stage structure that adjusts and maintains the position of the mirror. The payload utilizes optical elements, sensors, actuators, and control systems needed to maintain the stability and precision of the mirror position. [18]

In third-generation gravitational wave detectors, like the Einstein Telescope (ET), cryogenic payloads are introduced for thermal noise reduction [13]. Furthermore, the detectors are placed underground to reduce seismic noise. Both of these innovations enable the detector to achieve higher sensitivity, especially at the aimed low frequency sensitivity range of ET between 3-30 Hz. [13, 19]

In the cryogenic payloads, it is essential to minimize parasitic heat load, as it uses up the total available cooling power [20]. Electrical wires, which are essential for powering the instruments within the payload, are one of the parasitic heat load sources. The electrical wires generate heat due to Joule heat and also transfer heat into the cryogenic system as they transition from room temperature to low temperatures. The parasitic heat load introduced by the electrical wires is often overlooked, and the negative consequences may only become apparent during the operation, which underscores the importance of this thesis. [21]

The primary objective of this thesis is to design the electrical wiring system for the ET-LF cryogenic payload with an optimized configuration that minimizes parasitic heat load while ensuring reliable electrical operation at cryogenic temperatures.

This thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive overview of electrical wires, including their thermal behavior and how wire dimensions and materials influence performance in cryogenic conditions. Chapter 3 introduces the concept of gravitational wave detectors, with a focus on the payload and its components, including the electrical instruments and wiring systems. This chapter also presents a detailed study of two existing gravitational wave detectors, Advanced Virgo Plus (AdV+) and KAGRA, with a particular attention given to their payload designs, electrical instruments, and wiring. The design requirements for the ET are then discussed, followed by a proposed electrical instrument design based on a comparison of AdV+ and KAGRA.

Chapter 4 explains the methodology developed to optimize wire dimensions for minimal parasitic heat load, with an example calculation provided to clarify the methodology. The GRAVITHELIUM test cryostat, a test facility to measure the quality factors of cryogenic suspension materials relevant to the ET, is introduced, and the electrical wiring system for this test facility is optimized using the proposed methodology.

Chapter 5 evaluates six thermal scenarios for the electrical wiring system of the ET-LF payload, each based on two different cooling concepts. The performance of these scenarios is evaluated to identify the optimal configuration. A material study is then conducted to finalize the wiring design, ensuring the lowest possible parasitic heat load. The final design for the electrical wiring system of the ET-LF payload is presented at the conclusion of the chapter.

2. Theoretical background

This chapter aims to provide the groundwork for understanding and modeling the thermal behavior of electrical wires at cryogenic temperatures. The mathematical model presented in section 2.3 is based on the work of E. Shabagin [22] and design guidelines for electrical wires proposed by R. Poggiani for the Einstein Telescope project, funded by the European Commission [23], with adjustments made to fit the specific needs and constraints of this study.

2.1 Electrical cables and wires

An electrical cable is an assembly of one or more wires running side by side or bundled, used to transmit electric current [24]. It typically consists of wires that conduct electricity and insulation materials that ensure the current flows in the intended direction, as depicted in Figure 2.1 [25].

Electrical cables can be classified into power cables and signal cables [26]. Power cables supply relatively high, continuous electric current (AC or DC) to power devices or electronic systems. On the other hand, signal cables carry time-varying, low currents (typically AC) to convey information as signals in electronic systems. [27]

Electrical wires are identified primarily by their diameter size, using the American Wire Gauge (AWG) system, where a higher gauge number corresponds to a smaller wire diameter [28]. The integration of electrical wires into a cable requires selecting them according to their electrical requirements and twisting them [29]. Wires are typically twisted in pairs or triplets, to avoid noise pickup [30]. For instance, signal

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of an electrical cable, highlighting its main parts

cables are twisted depending on their frequency range to avoid crosstalk and electromagnetic interference [27]. Similarly, power cables can also be twisted, primarily based on their current-carrying capacity and insulation requirements [31]. For both power and signal cables, twisted wires are subsequently coated with insulation materials [25].

Electrical wires are commonly used to power electrical instruments in vacuum spaces between low-temperature and high-temperature sections of cryogenic systems [32]. Both the temperature gradient between the ambient and the cryogenic system and the resistive heating caused by continuous electric current conducted contribute to so-called parasitic heat leaks from the wires into the cryogenic system [21]. This can be a problem considering that parasitic heat loads reduce the available cooling power of the cryogenic system. A significant portion of the cooling power may be consumed to compensate for this, especially if the thermal design of the cryogenic system is not optimized for efficiency. [33]. Hence, electrical wires for cryogenic applications must be designed to minimize the parasitic heat load on the system [34].

2.2 Wire material properties

When wires carry electric current, they generate heat due to resistive losses, called the Joule heat \dot{Q}_I :

$$\dot{Q}_I = R(T) \cdot I^2 = \frac{\rho(T) \cdot L}{A} \cdot I^2 \quad (2.1)$$

,where I is the current, L the length and A the cross-section area of the wire [35]. The material- and temperature-dependent term of \dot{Q}_I , the electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$, typically decreases at cryogenic temperatures [23]. For materials such as copper or aluminum, another additional factor is used to define their electrical resistivity, the so-called Residual Resistivity Ratio (RRR). The RRR is the ratio between the electrical resistivity of the material at the ice point ($T = 273K$) and the residual electrical resistivity measured at the liquid helium normal boiling point ($T = 4.22K$), shown in equation 2.2. The RRR provides a measure of how well a material can maintain low resistivity when cooled down to cryogenic temperatures. [36]

$$\text{RRR} = \frac{\rho_{273 \text{ K}}}{\rho_{4.22 \text{ K}}} \quad (2.2)$$

As the temperature of the wire increases due to Joule heat, its specific electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ also rises, leading to a loop of further heating according to the equation 2.1. Beyond a certain temperature, the excessive heat adversely affects the electrical performance of the wire and can result into physical damage of the conductor or insulation. To mitigate this, a maximum current limit I_{\max} , known as the ampacity, is defined. One method to determine the ampacity of electrical wires is based on a fixed Joule heat criterion, which sets an upper limit on the generated volumetric Joule heat $Q_{I,\max}$. This limit is defined based on application-specific requirements, such as the temperature or available cooling power. The ampacity can be determined using the following equation [37]:

$$I_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{Q_{I,\max}}{\rho(T)}} \cdot A \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.2: Thermal conductivity of various materials as a function of temperature [1]

As seen from the equation 2.3, ampacity depends on the cross-section area A and electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ and therefore the temperature T . Electrical wires in cryogenic systems are designed according to their ampacity limit [38]. Generally, electrical wires are either directly immersed in cryogenic liquid or exposed to cryogenic liquid through windings to cool the wires [37]. However, these methods are not applicable in “cryogen-free” systems where the electrical wires are not in contact with the liquid. One possible solution is to use conduction cooling, where electrical wires are cooled only by one refrigeration unit at their cold end [22]. The conductive heat load \dot{Q}_λ is defined by Fourier’s Law:

$$\dot{Q}_\lambda = -\lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} \quad (2.4)$$

,where $\lambda(T)$ is the thermal conductivity as a function of temperature [39]. Although electrical resistivity generally decreases at low temperatures, thermal conductivity can, for some materials, increase (see Figure 2.2) [23]. This opposition requires the careful selection of materials, as they must have low electrical resistivity to minimize Joule heat, while also exhibiting low thermal conductivity to limit heat transfer to the surrounding environment. For instance, from the figure 2.2 it is evident that although pure copper has a higher value of RRR and therefore better electrical conductivity, Oxygen Free High Conductivity (OFHC) copper is a better option for electrical wiring in a cryogenic environment due to its lower thermal conductivity. Hence, for the wires of power cables, copper is commonly used as the

conductor material [34]. On the other hand for the wires of signal cables, alloys such as manganin and constantan are often used due to their relatively constant resistivity and low thermal conductivity at cryogenic temperatures [40].

2.3 Thermal analysis of electrical wires

The thermal analysis presented in this section focuses on a homogeneous wire with a cross section area A and length L , characterized by a specific electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ and thermal conductivity $\lambda(T)$, where the temperature T is assumed to vary only along the axial direction x , as shown in Figure 2.3. The start of the wire length, the so-called cold end, is assumed on the coldest temperature T_c , while the wire length ends on the warm end (at room temperature) T_h . In a steady-state energy balance for the wire, a heat load from the warmer end \dot{Q}_h is conducted through the wire. Along the wire length, a significant amount of \dot{Q}_I occurs due to the carried current, both \dot{Q}_h and \dot{Q}_I accumulates on the cold end of the wire as the cold end heat load \dot{Q}_c , which is then extracted from the system.

Figure 2.3: Scheme of a conduction cooled electrical wire

The energy balance of the infinitesimal segment of the wire enclosed between the dashed lines in Figure 2.3 is:

$$\dot{Q}_\lambda(x+dx) - \dot{Q}_\lambda(x) + d\dot{Q}_I = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

, where $\dot{Q}_\lambda(x)$ is the conducted heat out of the segment position x , $d\dot{Q}_I$ the generated Joule heat and $\dot{Q}_\lambda(x+dx)$ the heat conducted into the segment at position $(x+dx)$. The term $\dot{Q}_\lambda(x+dx)$ in equation 2.5 can be simplified using a first-order Taylor expansion around x :

$$\dot{Q}_\lambda(x+dx) \approx \dot{Q}_\lambda(x) - \frac{\partial \dot{Q}_\lambda}{\partial x} \cdot dx \quad (2.6)$$

The substitution of the term $\dot{Q}_\lambda(x+dx)$ from equation 2.6 into equation 2.5 gives:

$$\dot{Q}_\lambda(x) - \frac{\partial \dot{Q}_\lambda}{\partial x} \cdot dx - \dot{Q}_\lambda(x) + d\dot{Q}_I = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

and the equation 2.7 can be simplified into:

$$-d\dot{Q}_\lambda + d\dot{Q}_I = 0. \quad (2.8)$$

The equation 2.8 can be expanded into partial differential forms with respect to x :

$$-\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Q}_\lambda}{\partial x}\right) dx + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Q}_I}{\partial x}\right) dx = 0 \quad (2.9)$$

The substitution of the partial differential terms in equation 2.9 with the equations 2.4 and 2.1 results in:

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-\lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(I^2 \cdot \frac{\rho(T)}{A} \cdot dx \right) = 0. \quad (2.10)$$

It is important to note that the term $\frac{\partial T}{\partial x}$ in equation 2.10 is negative due to the defined system coordinates in figure 2.3. The following equation is obtained by simplifying the equation 2.10:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + I^2 \cdot \frac{\rho(T)}{A} = 0. \quad (2.11)$$

The equation 2.11 is a steady-state one-dimensional, second-order differential equation [22, 23]. The axial temperature distribution for the wire shown in Figure 2.3 can be determined by solving the equation 2.11. Two Dirichlet boundary conditions are defined for the solution of the differential equation 2.11:

$$T_{(x=L)} = T_h \stackrel{(e.g.)}{=} 300 \text{ K} \quad (2.12)$$

$$T_{(x=0)} = T_c \stackrel{(e.g.)}{=} 60 \text{ K or } 5 \text{ K} \quad (2.13)$$

$T_{(x=0)}$ represents the temperature of the starting point of the wire, the cold end; while $T_{(x=L)}$ is the end point of the wire, the warm end. The temperature distribution $T(x)$ of the wire can be obtained by solving the equation 2.11 with the boundary conditions 2.13 and 2.12. The equation 2.1 can be combined with the temperature distribution $T(x)$ to calculate the total Joule heat generated along the wire, via integration along the length, as follows:

$$\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}} = \frac{I^2}{A} \cdot \int_0^L \rho(T(x)) dx \quad (2.14)$$

The conducted heat load on the warm end ($x = L$) according to Fourier's Law 2.4 is:

$$\dot{Q}_h = -\lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \text{for } x \rightarrow L \quad (2.15)$$

and the conducted heat load on the cold end ($x = 0$) using $T(x)$:

$$\dot{Q}_c = -\lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \text{for } x \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.16)$$

In conclusion, the energy balance for the total length of the wire is:

$$\dot{Q}_c = \dot{Q}_h + \dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}. \quad (2.17)$$

The design goal is to minimize the heat load on the cold end of the wire, \dot{Q}_c . The design of the wire must account for several factors simultaneously, including the ampacity, the wire's geometric dimensions, the material properties (thermal

conductivity and electrical resistivity), and the current the wire needs to carry in order to meet the electrical requirements of the application.

The examination of the dependence of the heat load \dot{Q}_c on the wire geometry indicates the fundamental design challenge: The heat load \dot{Q}_c is proportional to the cross section area and inversely proportional to the length, favoring long thin wires. However, Joule heat $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$, and therefore \dot{Q}_c according to the equation 2.17, can be reduced by choosing thick and short wires. These effects oppose each other. Nevertheless, the requirement that the current carried by the wire must always remain below the ampacity limit, as explained in section 2.2, ensures that the smallest possible diameter is targeted, as it minimizes the overall heat load \dot{Q}_c .

To adjust the remaining parameters based on a fixed parameter, such as the diameter, the shape-factor S can be used:

$$S = \frac{I \cdot L}{A} = f(T_c, T_h, \lambda(T), \rho(T)) \quad (2.18)$$

The shape-factor S represents the optimal ratio of the length, cross-section area, and current for a wire between the temperatures T_c and T_h , as it is derived based on the theoretical minimum of \dot{Q}_c . S is a function of the temperature and material properties. The derivation of the shape-factor function is as follows:

The equation 2.1 is differentiated with respect to x .

$$d\dot{Q}_I = \frac{\rho(T) \cdot I^2}{A} \cdot dx \quad (2.19)$$

By isolating dx in Fourier's law 2.4, the following equation is obtained:

$$dx = \frac{-\lambda(T) \cdot A}{\dot{Q}_\lambda} \cdot dT \quad (2.20)$$

The combination of the equations 2.19 and 2.20 results in the following:

$$d\dot{Q}_I = \frac{-\lambda(T) \cdot \rho(T) \cdot I^2}{\dot{Q}_\lambda} \cdot dT \quad (2.21)$$

The equation 2.21 can be combined with 2.8

$$d\dot{Q}_I = d\dot{Q}_\lambda = \frac{-\lambda(T) \cdot \rho(T) \cdot I^2}{\dot{Q}_\lambda} \cdot dT \quad (2.22)$$

Variable separation to the equation 2.22 and integrating accordingly leads to:

$$\int_{\dot{Q}_c}^{\dot{Q}_h} \dot{Q}_\lambda d\dot{Q}_\lambda = -I^2 \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT \quad (2.23)$$

$$\frac{\dot{Q}_c^2}{2} - \frac{\dot{Q}_h^2}{2} = I^2 \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT \quad (2.24)$$

The solution of the equation 2.24 for \dot{Q}_c is:

$$\dot{Q}_c = \sqrt{(\dot{Q}_h)^2 + 2 \cdot I^2 \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT} \quad (2.25)$$

According to the equation 2.25, \dot{Q}_c can only be minimum, when the heat load from the warm end is equal to zero:

$$\dot{Q}_h \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (2.26)$$

The adiabatic boundary condition from the equation 2.26 applied to the equation 2.25 results in a theoretical minimum value for the conducted heat at the cold end:

$$\dot{Q}_{c,\min} = \sqrt{2 \cdot I^2 \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT} \quad (2.27)$$

$\dot{Q}_{c,\min}$ can be written with Fourier's Law (Eq. 2.4):

$$|\dot{Q}_{c,\min}| = \lambda(T) \cdot A \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} = I \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT} \quad (2.28)$$

The separation of the variables, followed by the integration of the equation 2.28 yields:

$$\frac{I}{A} \cdot \int_0^L dx = \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \frac{\lambda(T)}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \int_T^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT}} dT \quad (2.29)$$

The lower boundary of the integral in equation 2.28 is changed to the variable T for the calculation of the shape-factor. Lastly, the integration on the right-hand side of the equation 2.29 can be solved and the shape-factor S can be obtained as:

$$S = \left(\frac{I \cdot L}{A} \right) = \int_{T_c}^{T_h} \frac{\lambda(T)}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \int_T^{T_h} \rho(T) \cdot \lambda(T) dT}} dT. \quad (2.30)$$

3. State of the art: Gravitational Wave Detectors

Gravitational wave detectors are advanced scientific instruments designed to measure ripples in spacetime, the gravitational waves, caused by massive accelerating objects, such as merging black holes or neutron stars [16]. Gravitational waves induce small distortions in spacetime, resulting in slight stretching or compression of distances [41]. These distortions are not identical along the x- and y-axes, which allows for the detection of gravitational waves. Laser interferometry is used to measure these variations by detecting differences in the time it takes for laser light to travel along the detector's arms, enabling the identification of these distortions along the x and y axes. [42]

The Figure 3.1 shows a typical interferometry configuration of a gravitational wave detector. Generally, gravitational wave detectors are based on Michelson Interferometry. The laser first goes through the power recycling mirror (PR) to recycle the reflected light off detector. The beam splitter (BS) is used to split the laser light into two beams. This is followed by the input- and end-mirrors (ITM and ETM), which forms a Fabry-Perot cavity together. They enhance the interaction time of the laser within the detector. Lastly, the signal recycling mirror (SR) allows to redirect the signal back to the interferometer, to improve the strength of the signal. [2].

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of a typical interferometer configuration. [2]

This thesis focuses on the input- and end-mirrors. To ensure accurate detection, these mirrors within the detector must remain exceptionally unaffected by external disturbances, as the measurement is highly sensitive to both temporal and positional disturbances [43]. To achieve this level of isolation, the suspension system incorporates an inverted pendulum configuration at its upper stages, which provides enhanced low-frequency isolation from seismic noise. SA towers are engineered to maintain the precise positioning of the mirrors by mitigating vibrations, especially caused by seismic noise [44]. These towers typically consist of multiple suspension stages, and an inverted pendulum, each designed to detect and attenuate mechanical disturbances, isolating the mirrors from the external noise sources, especially seismic noise [18].

The payload is a crucial component of the gravitational wave detector that consists of the final stages of SA tower, including its core element, the mirror, and immediate support structures [45]. It is engineered to provide fine control and additional isolation from residual vibrations. The payload minimizes external noise and ensures the accuracy of interferometric measurements by suspending the mirror and adjusting its position with extreme precision.[18]

This chapter includes an overview of the payloads in gravitational wave detectors, focusing on the technologies used for electrical instruments and cabling within the payload structures. It then introduces the payload of AdV+ and the cryogenic payload of KAGRA. Since the ET has not yet been constructed, this chapter outlines the general design requirements and the preliminary design for the ET payload structure. The chapter concludes with a proposal for the instrumentation of the ET payload, drawing existing payloads as a reference.

Figure 3.2: Schematic representation of the payload structure including platform, marionette, test mass and reaction mass

3.1 Gravitational Wave Detector Payloads

The payload is placed inside a vacuum chamber, suspended from the SA and includes specially designed final stage suspensions to minimize environmental disturbances such as thermal noise, seismic noise, and air damping [18]. The payload consists of three main components: platform, marionette, and test mass, as shown in Figure 3.2. The platform is responsible of isolating the whole payload from vibrations and suspends the marionette. The marionette provides an intermediate suspension stage between the platform and the test mass. The test mass is the mirror for gravitational wave detection. In addition, the structure called the reaction mass serves as a reaction mass for the system, and is mostly directly suspended from the platform. It houses the necessary instruments required for operation, to prevent direct contact with the sensitive optical elements. The reaction mass can consist of either multiple suspended stages, arranged like a chain, or alternatively, it can be a rigid structure, known as the “cage”, which effectively combines the multiple stages. [13]

3.1.1 Payload Instrumentation

There are several instruments used inside the payload, which can be classified both by their location and their purpose of use. To explain their necessity, this section first categorizes them based on their purpose: displacement measurement, position adjustment, and thermal and optical management, as summarized in Figure 3.3. All components work based on a feedback-control loop: First, the instruments measure the displacement and send feedback signals to the control system. Based on this feedback, the instruments adjust the position of the components accordingly. This process allows for precise position control, ensuring the payload remains stable and aligned. [46]

Displacement Measurement: Four types of sensors are commonly used for measuring the displacement of the payload parts, as summarized in Figure 3.3. Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) sensors function by passing alternating current through a primary coil to generate a magnetic field. This field induces voltages in two secondary coils. A ferromagnetic core moves within the coil assembly, causing the voltage in one secondary coil to increase while decreasing in the other. The output voltage, proportional to the core’s displacement, is the difference between the two secondary voltages. This allows precise measurement of linear dis-

Figure 3.3: Classification of general electrical instruments used in a payload.

placement when mounted on a body. [47] Therefore, LVDTs are typically used in both the payload and SA tower to measure their linear displacement [48].

Furthermore, sensors including photodiodes and Light-Emitting Diode (LED) are essential for displacement measurement [8]. The LED emits light and it is reflected on the surface of payload components. The amount of detected light on photodiode changes in distance between the sensor body and reflecting surface. Therefore, relative displacement between two bodies, for instance between the marionette and the reaction mass, can be measured. [49]

Piezo actuators are used as additional displacement measuring sensors for the platform; the sensors of piezo actuators measure the deformation of piezoelectric materials, which expand or contract due to the displacement of the platform [50, 51].

Position Adjustment: Stepper motors, picomotors and piezo actuators are commonly used in a payload for position adjustment [3]. Stepper motors operate using electromagnetic fields; the rotor is moved step-wise, as the motors coils are energized in a specific sequence [52]. They are responsible for rotating or aligning the platform and the marionette around the vertical or horizontal axes. In gravitational wave detectors, fine adjustments to the center of gravity of the payload are essential to maintain alignment and compensate for drifts over time [18]. In order to achieve this, some stepper motors are incorporated with mechanical trolleys to move small masses, to slightly shift the center of gravity of payload parts. [45]

Additionally, picomotors are adapted to adjust the positions of optical elements [3], since they provide more sensitive movements in comparison to stepper motors. In a picomotor, piezoelectric or electrostatic materials expand or contract, which push or pull the load with nanometer- or sub-nanometer-scale precision, when voltage is applied. [53] Piezo actuators can be used for not only displacement measurement, but also position adjustment. The piezoelectric material in a piezo actuator expands or contracts when voltage is applied, and this deformation can be used to position the attached body. [51].

Moreover, coil-magnet pairs are mounted on different parts of the payload to generate controlled forces and torques. In this system, the coils, which serve as the active elements, are attached to the recoil mass, while the magnets act as passive elements. [18] When an electric current flows through the coils, a magnetic field is induced, interacting with the permanent magnets to apply force without physical contact [54]. The strength and direction of the force can be precisely controlled by adjusting the current [55]. This contact-free actuation method is particularly important for mirror positioning, as it eliminates mechanical contact, thereby minimizing disturbances and preventing unwanted noise that could affect optical performance [56].

Thermal and Optical Management: Temperature sensors are the primary instruments for thermal management in a payload. High-power laser beams introduce significant heat loads to optical components, leading to a rise in temperature. [57] This is particularly critical for mirrors, as temperature fluctuations alter the refractive index of the material, affecting optical performance [58]. To mitigate this, temperature sensors continuously monitor the thermal conditions of mirrors and other critical components, allowing for active compensation when needed [3].

For cryogenic operations, temperature sensors play an even more essential role. Since components operate at extremely low temperatures in cryogenic payloads, precise thermal monitoring is required to maintain stability and prevent unwanted thermal gradients [59, 60]. These sensors ensure that the payload remains within

optimal operating conditions, supporting both optical performance and structural integrity throughout operation.

Stray light in gravitational wave detectors can potentially limit the performance at low frequencies. This issue was recognized long ago, navigating the development of a structure, the so-called baffle, which is placed in front of the mirror. Baffles can be equipped with additional sensors such as photodiodes, to measure the amount of scattered light. [61]

Additional instruments are specifically designed to mitigate unwanted thermal and optical effects in the mirror. However, these instruments are detector-specific and are not implemented universally across all payloads. Therefore, their detailed explanations are provided in their respective detector sections.

Cabling is needed for the electrical connection between sensors, coils and motors inside the payload and the electronics outside [3]. Cable design is a crucial consideration as cables affect their environment for various reasons and need to be made robust due to the long time they are in operation. Their design and installation requires special planning considering the high amount of cables. In cryogenic gravitational wave detectors, additional constraints arise, as cables must not only function reliably but also minimize parasitic heat load on the cryostat. Their material and geometry play a critical role in achieving both electrical performance and thermal efficiency. The design requirements can be divided into the following categories [23]:

Environmental aspects: Power cables carry high values of continuous currents in comparison to signal cables [26], 2. Hence, their heat leakage due to Joule heating over time needs to be minimized, particularly in a cryogenic system where heat extraction is challenging. In room-temperature detectors, Joule heating is primarily a concern to prevent cable failure or burning. However, in cryogenic detectors, it is an even more critical issue, as every additional heat input increases the cooling demand and affects the overall thermal stability of the payload. The choice of cable material and geometry is essential in cryogenic environments to limit parasitic heat load into the cryostat. Materials with low thermal conductivity are preferred to reduce conductive heat transfer along the cable path, while the cross-sectional dimensioning must be based on electrical requirements and heat load constraints, as discussed in Chapter 2 [34] Additionally, all materials used in cabling should have a low outgassing rate to ensure compatibility with the vacuum environment [62].

Electrical and electromagnetic aspects: All cables should be electrically compatible in terms of ampacity, electromagnetic interference and impedance [63]. In cryogenic detectors, ampacity must be carefully analyzed, as resistance changes with temperature, as explained in Chapter 2. The choice of conductor material must therefore account for its cryogenic performance, ensuring stable operation across temperature gradients. The unintentional transfer of electrical signals or interference in a conductor caused by nearby conductors (crosstalk) should be avoided, especially in signal cables [3, 64]. Lastly, cables should have high-quality electrical insulation from external electromagnetic fields or from ground loops [64].

Installation aspects: The cables should have overall high mechanical flexibility for installation purposes and should be clamped at suitable points. In cryogenic systems, thermal contraction must also be considered, as materials shrink at low temperatures, which can introduce mechanical stress if not properly managed. In case of a malfunction, the cables should be easily accessible for problem identification and/or cable replacement. [3] Cables connected to the mirror coils are highly sensitive (e.g. to inductive coupling) therefore, they must be properly shielded and

driven [65]. In cryogenic payloads, thermal insulation of cables is another important factor, as it helps to reduce unwanted heat load into the cold parts of the cryostat.

3.2 Advanced Virgo Plus (AdV+)

The Virgo Interferometer, a first-generation gravitational wave detector near Pisa, Italy, is a recycled Michelson interferometer with 3 km long Fabry-Perot cavities [66]. Virgo is designed to achieve a strain sensitivity of a few times $10^{-23}\text{Hz}^{-1/2}$ at 200 Hz and noise reduction to $10^{-21}\text{Hz}^{-1/2}$ at 10 Hz [67]. Virgo operated for over a decade without detections. However, the results enabled advancements in interferometer research and development [68]. In the early 2000s, Virgo was upgraded to Advanced Virgo (AdVirgo) to improve sensitivity by one order of magnitude and increase detection rates by three orders of magnitude, transforming it into a second generation gravitational wave detector [69]. AdVirgo was further improved into AdV+, implemented in two phases: Phase I focusing on quantum noise reduction by increasing laser power, introducing signal recycling, and adding a frequency-dependent vacuum squeezed source, while Phase II, which is currently under implementation, aims to reduce thermal noise through larger, high-mass mirrors and improved coatings [3].

The passive seismic noise isolation of AdV+ is achieved through SA towers, which reduce seismic noise by over 10 orders of magnitude above a few Hz [70]. The SA consists of a 5-stage pendulum supported by a 3-leg inverted pendulum pre-isolator, as presented in Figure 3.4a. The system includes the filter 0, providing mechanical support and controlling large displacements below 10 mHz, and four standard filters (filters 1-4) designed for vertical attenuation using maraging steel blades and magnetic anti-spring systems. Filter 7, located above the payload as show in Figure 3.4a, is specifically designed to steer the payload. [44]

(a) 3D image of SA tower of AdV+ including the payload

(b) 3D image of Filter 7 showing its components in detail

Figure 3.4: 3D images of an SA tower (a) and the Filter 7 (b) of AdV+ [3]

Figure 3.5: CAD drawing of the assembled payload in AdV+. The drawing includes actuator cage excluded mounts for components located around the mirror, cage components and their mounts (ring heater, baffles, actuators), marionette and its components [4]

3.2.1 Room-temperature Payload of AdV+

The payload of AdV+ is located inside a vacuum chamber to reach higher sensitivity [69]. The structure of the payload includes the platform, the marionette and the test mass [45]. The filter 7 is the connection part between the SA tower and the payload of AdV+, however, it will be presented in this subsection as the platform of the payload, since it serves similar functions as of a platform. The payload includes a cage structure called the actuator cage, which serves as the reaction mass and houses the electrical instruments, as shown in Figure 3.5. This subsection focuses on the payload of AdV+ Phase II, providing an overview of its design and implemented electrical instruments. The presented design summary is based on Advanced Virgo Plus Phase II Design Report [3] and presentation on Advanced Virgo suspensions and mirrors by V. Boschi, from the Virgo Collaboration [45].

3.2.1.1 The Platform (Filter 7)

A 3D image of the Filter 7 is shown in Figure 3.4b. Filter 7 is specifically designed to steer the payload, equipped with 4 aluminum legs, which are used for mechanical support. The legs are about 900 mm long and 250 mm in diameter, bolted on the bottom part of the filter body, as shown in Figure 3.4a.

Filter 7 includes various sensors for displacement measurement: 6 LVDTs measure the linear displacement of the Filter 7. Additionally, 3 piezo actuators are implemented as displacement measurement sensors (see Subsection 3.1.1). The piezo actuators are installed corresponding to the geometry of the inverted pendulum top stage (pinwheel configuration at 120° from one other). Piezo actuators and LVDTs send feedback signals for the feedback-control loop. Based on these signals, the control is executed via position adjustment instruments, the motors and the coils.

One of the four stepper motors is located on top of the filter body and used for rotating the filter with respect to the upper part of the SA together with the whole payload. A second stepper motor is under the filter and used for adjusting the

Table 3.1: Electrical wire connections of Filter 7 (platform) [15].

Component	Quantity	Wire diameter	Twisting
LVDT	6	0.3 mm	6 twisted pairs
stepper motor	4	0.6 mm	2 twisted pairs
coils	6	0.3 mm	1 twisted triplet
fishing rod motor	1	unknown	unknown
piezo actuator	3	unknown	unknown

Table 3.2: Electrical wire connections of the marionette [15]

Component	Quantity	Wire diameter	Twisting
actuation coils	8	0.6 mm	8 twisted pairs
stepper motor	2	0.6 mm	2 twisted pairs
		0.3 mm	1 twisted triplet

relative positions of the coils and magnets. Additionally, two stepper motors move two small masses attached to mechanical trolleys on top of the filter body, for fine adjustments of the rotations around the two horizontal axes [18]. Another motor is used for the fishing rod part of the Filter 7. Besides the motors, 6 coils are utilized for the position adjustment. The Table 3.1 summarizes the electrical wires for the Filter 7.

3.2.1.2 The Marionette

The marionette steers the test mass as its main function and serves as an intermediary suspension stage. It is suspended with a single maraging steel wire, has an octagonal shape and is made of 316L amagnetic steel. The marionette has stepper motors and coils for the position adjustment. Two stepper motors move high density copper-tungsten alloy counterweights to slightly shift the center of gravity [4]. Additionally, eight coils mounted on the actuator cage work together with the magnets on the marionette, to adjust the position of the marionette. The Table 3.2 shows the electrical wiring of the components associated with the marionette.

3.2.1.3 The Test Mass

The AdV+ detector has highly precise optical components to ensure optimal sensitivity. The mirrors are constructed from fused silica, a material which has exceptional optical transparency and low thermal expansion coefficient [71]. 8 coils are used for the position adjustment. The coils are mounted on the respective part of the actuator cage while the magnets are on the mirror. The electrical wires for the coils are presented in Table 3.3.

Unlike the marionette and the platform, the test mass has specifically designed instruments for thermal and optical management: compensation plate, ring heater and baffle. Compensation plates are introduced to maintain the stability of the mirrors and prevent distortions caused by the amplitude noise of the laser beam. These plates are also made from fused silica and are placed only in front of the input-

(a) Actuation scheme of the AdV+: blue rectangles represent the compensation plates (CP) after the beam splitter (BS) while the green dots around the test masses are the ring heaters (RH).

(b) image of an input mirror including a ring heater and a compensation plate

Figure 3.6: Actuation scheme of the AdV+ (a) and image of mirror-compensation plate configuration (b) [5]

Table 3.3: Electrical wire connections of a ring heater (RH), compensation plate (CP) and the coils of the mirror [15]

Component	Quantity	Wire diameter	Twisting
PT100 temperature sensor (RH)	2	0.6 mm	4 twisted pairs
picomotor (RH)	2	0.6 mm	4 twisted pairs
NiCr wire coil	2	0.6 mm	2 twisted pairs
picomotor (CP)	2	0.6 mm	4 twisted pairs
coils	8	0.6 mm	4 twisted pairs

mirrors to adjust and stabilize the wavefront of the laser beam. The configuration of the mirror with a compensation plate can be seen in Figure 3.6b.

Additionally, Hartmann Wave-Front Sensors (HWS) are incorporated into the compensation plates to measure the thermally induced distortions. The HWS devices are hosted in a custom housing, designed to improve the thermal inertia of the sensor and its analog to digital converter, in order to increase the temperature stability of the HWS. Moreover, the compensation plates are equipped with two picomotors, offering nanometer-scale precision with very slow and controlled movements [53]. The electrical wiring for the picomotors of the compensation plates in AdV+ payload are summarized in Table 3.3.

Ring heaters are specifically designed to heat up the borders of the mirror. This heating is necessary because high laser power causes temperature variations along the mirror. Since the refraction index of the mirror is highly temperature-dependent, the temperature variations can lead to disturbances in the optical path [58]. To mitigate this issue, ring heaters heat up the border of the input- and end-mirror and allow a uniform temperature profile along the mirror. Ring heaters are utilized both in input- and end-mirrors, as shown in Figure 3.6a.

The ring heater is composed of two parallel borosilicate glass formers, heated up by Joule effect through two NiCr wire coils and surrounded by a polisher copper shield. The coils are assembled in counter flux configuration to reduce the stray magnetic field gradient. The wires carry a maximum of 1 A current and are supplied by a DC module. A ring heater generates 40 W joule heat. The ring heaters are equipped with platinum temperature sensors (PT100) and picomotors, for fine position adjustments. The electrical wiring for the ring heater including the ring heater coils, temperature sensors and the picomotors are summarized in Table 3.3.

The last instrument for the thermal and optical management, the baffles, are made out of stainless steel 304L. They have the shape of an annular disc and are mechanically supported by the actuator cage. The baffles are placed in front of the mirrors, to mitigated the issues caused by the scattered light (see Subsection 3.1.1). To measure the amount of scattered light, they include photodiodes. Each baffle is sectioned with two halves and each half is divided in three sectors, which are equipped with a printed circuit board that contains a micro-controller, 3 analog to digital converters and 42 photodiodes. In total there are 252 photodiodes (model S15468) from Hamamatsu per baffle.

To provide a clear overview of the payload structure and the spatial distribution of its components, Figure 3.7 presents a schematic representation of the AdV+ payload. This diagram visually maps the key components discussed in this section, including the platform, marionette, test mass, actuator cage, and associated subsystems. It serves as a visual summary, illustrating the locations of the instruments such as the LVDT, stepper motors, picomotors, coils, and magnets. Additional structures, including the ring heater, instrumented baffle, and compensation plate, are also depicted to highlight their integration within the system. Table 3.4 further complements this visualization by providing a structured representation of the data. Moreover, Table A.1 in the appendix provides a comparison of electrical instruments between AdV+ and KAGRA.

Table 3.4: Overview of instruments in the payload of AdV+, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management)

Purpose of Use	Platform (Filter 7)	Marionette	Test Mass
Displacement Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 LVDTs • 3 piezo actuators 	• -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 252 photodiodes • With printed circuit board, microcontroller and analog to digital converter
Position Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 coils • 4 stepper motors • 1 motor for the fishing rod 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 coils • 2 stepper motors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 coils (mirror) • 2 picomotors (CP) • 2 picomotors (RH)
Thermal and Optical Management	• -	• -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ring heater (RH) • Compensation plate (CP) • Instrumented baffle (with HWS and photodiodes)

Figure 3.7: Schematic representation of AdV+ payload, illustrating the main structural components and key instrumentation, including displacement measurement, position adjustment and thermal compensation elements.

Figure 3.8: The images of the cables used between filter 4 and platform (filter 7), (left: before installation, right: after installation into the conductance pipe and mounting on filter 7 (platform)) [3].

3.2.1.4 Electrical Wiring of AdV+ Payload

In AdV+, electrical wires start their path from the front-end electronics in racks placed sideways each SA tower and go through all standard filters of SA. In total, there are about 450 wires per SA tower. After twisting the wires in pairs or triplets, they are installed along a conductance pipe with 740 mm length and 26 mm inner diameter, shown in Figure 3.8. The pipe is filled with special Araldite for casting and the ends of the pipe is sealed with MasterBond glue. The electrical wires passing via the connection from the filter 4 to the filter 7 are listed in the Tables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3. After the filter 7, the wires enter in the vacuum environment through a set of electrical feed-throughs mounted on the tower flanges, and reach the payload. [3]

While this thesis focuses on the electrical wiring for the ET-LF payload, the analysis of the electrical wires of AdV+ provides valuable insights. This analysis defines the system boundaries for the electrical wire design of ET-LF payload (presented in Chapter 5), where the electrical wires start from outside the system and extend into the payload.

3.3 KAGRA Interferometer

KAGRA is a 2.5 generation gravitational wave detector, located in Kamioka, Gifu, Japan. The interferometer configuration is an L-shape with a 3-km arm length. [72] Unlike the gravitational detectors of the second generation (e.g. AdVirgo), KAGRA is constructed underground, similar to the vision of third generation gravitational wave detectors to achieve better seismic noise isolation. Another key feature of KAGRA is that its four test masses (the input and end mirrors of the Fabry-Perot cavities along the x- and y-axes) are cryogenically cooled to 20 K, significantly reducing thermal noise. [73] In April 2020, KAGRA completed an observation run, the O3GK, at room temperature and achieved a strain sensitivity of $3 \times 10^{-22} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$ at 250 Hz [74]. In the next observation run O4, KAGRA is operating at cryogenic temperatures and will continue until June 2025 [75].

In the KAGRA Interferometer configuration, only the input- and end-mirrors are found inside cryostats in a vacuum environment. The suspension system for the cryogenic mirror is called Type-A suspension system, which is a 9-stage pendulum, shown in Figure 3.9a [72]. The first 5 stages, starting with the top filter and inverted pendulum, following with 3 Geometric Anti-Spring (GAS) filters and the bottom filter, operate at room temperature [6]. To stabilize many of the resonance motions in Type-A suspension, LVDTs are utilized [76]. The remaining 4 stages constituting the payload include the platform, the marionette, the intermediate mass and the test mass. The two radiation shields of the cryostat are cooled with very-low-vibration cryo-cooler units, resulting in an outer shield temperature of 80 K and inner shield 8 K [59]. Pure aluminum wires are braided together and used as heat links to cool down the payload. Due to the high power of the laser and the high bulk absorption of the test mass material (sapphire), the test mass reaches a temperature of approximately 20 K [77].

3.3.1 Cryogenic Payload of KAGRA

The payload of KAGRA, shown in Figure 3.9b, is designed as two suspension chains: the test mass chain, which includes the marionette, intermediate mass and the test mass, and the recoil mass chain including the recoil masses of the main chain. The latter holds the sensors and actuators [49, 78]. These two chains are suspended by the platform independently, as depicted in Figure 3.9a [55]. The cryostat includes cooling bars connected to Heat Link Vibraton Isolation Systems (HLVIS) for vibration isolation of the heat links. Heat links sequentially provide a conductive connection from the cooling bars to the HLVIS. From HLVIS, they first connect to the marionette, then extend from the marionette to the platform and intermediate mass, and finally from the intermediate mass to the test mass, as depicted in Figure 3.12. Each stage, including the corresponding recoil masses, is equipped with Cernox temperature sensors. [78, 79] The following subsections will explain the components of the payload, focusing primarily on the implemented electrical instruments.

Figure 3.9: The schematic of KAGRA Type-A suspension tower showing the arrangement of the room-temperature SA and cryogenic payload, including the thermal shields (80 K and 8 K) [6] (a) and the cryogenic Payload of KAGRA (b) [7]

3.3.1.1 Platform

The purpose of the platform is to isolate the test mass chain from vibration and align the recoil mass chain and the main chain [8]. The platform is the first cryogenic stage of the Type-A suspension system, suspended with one maraging steel wire [49]. In addition, the platform incorporates three CuBe blade springs, which provide vertical vibration isolation [7]. The platform hosts an inclination adjustment system, called moving mass system. The moving mass changes the center of mass of the platform, this results in inclination control on the two suspension chains, respectively [49]. The moving mass system was designed with ball screw to convert rotation of the motor into lateral motion of masses. It was later discovered that this design was not efficient, as the nuts occasionally became stuck after limited use due to the complex structure of the ball screw. The design was improved to function with kevlar wire and a pulley to avoid this issue, as shown in Figure 3.10. Additionally, the new system eliminates the need of constant DC current to hold the position of the moving mass [8]. The motors for the moving mass system are cryogenic-compatible stepper motors (model D42.2 UHV) from Arun Microelectronics [80].

3.3.1.2 Marionette and Intermediate Mass

The marionette is used to fine-tune the angle of the intermediate mass and the test mass to ensure proper alignment with the injected beam [78]. The marionette is suspended from the platform with one maraging steel suspension wire, while the recoil mass of the marionette is supported by three copper beryllium suspension wires [49]. The marionette is equipped with two types of position adjustment systems: the moving mass system and coil-magnet actuators. While the moving mass system has the same design as that of the platform, as depicted in Figure 3.10, six pairs of coil-

magnet actuators enable actuation in six degrees of freedom [49]. SmCo magnets are mounted directly to the marionette, while the corresponding coils are mounted on the marionette's recoil mass [55]. Each coil for the marionette receives a maximum current of 9.4 mA [81].

Two types of displacement sensors are suggested for the marionette: OSEM and reflective photo sensor, illustrated in Figure 3.11 [82]. OSEM is a compact device used for displacement measurement and actuation. It consists of an LED that emits a light beam toward a photodiode, which detects positional changes based on the amount of light received. Simultaneously, an electrical current passing through the coil generates an electromagnetic force, interacting with a nearby magnet to provide actuation. The total length of the wire for coil winding is expected to be 53 m with a 28 AWG inner diameter and carries a maximum current of 100 mA, resulting in approximately 0.1 W heat load due to Joule heating per OSEM [9].

The reflective photo sensor includes two photodiodes and one LED. The LED emits light towards the target, and the reflected light is measured via the photodiodes. The change of the amount of reflected light is equivalent to the displacement [8]. KAGRA adopts the reflective photo sensor as the cryogenic displacement sensor, due to its wide dynamic range and cryogenic compatibility [82]. In total there are six reflective photo sensors mounted on the marionette's recoil mass [83]. The photodiodes (model FGA21) and LEDs (model LED1200E) used in the reflective photo sensor were sourced from Thorlabs [84, 85].

Figure 3.10: Image of the new moving mass system used in the platform and the marionette [8]

Figure 3.11: The schematics of suggested displacement sensors for the KAGRA Payload: reflective photo sensor (a) [8] and OSEM from two different view points [9] (b)

The intermediate mass is the suspension stage between the marionette and test mass, suspending the test mass with sapphire blade springs. The design and the electrical components of the intermediate mass are similar to the marionette, yet without a moving mass system. Additionally, optical levers are used to measure the displacement of KAGRA’s marionette, intermediate mass and test mass, but as they are located outside the cryostat, they exceed the scope of this thesis and will not be further discussed. [49]

3.3.1.3 Test Mass

The mirror is suspended from the intermediate mass by four sapphire fibers, while the recoil mass of the test mass is supported by three copper-beryllium suspension wires [49]. The mirror is made of sapphire, a material selected for its high thermal conductivity and low-dissipative behavior (high quality factors) at cryogenic temperatures [86]. Four coil-magnet actuators enable fine-tuning adjustments with the same configuration as explained for the marionette [83]. The test mass coils receive less current than the ones in marionette and intermediate mass, precisely 1.7 mA [81]. To reduce thermal radiation and prevent scattered light, wide angle baffles coated with Solblack are installed in front of the mirror. However, the baffles are not a part of the payload, but they are located on the cryostat. [60, 87]

This subchapter reviewed the current technologies and components implemented in KAGRA, with a particular focus on its cryogenic payload. However, unlike the detailed insights available for AdV+ in the Section 3.2.1, the publicly accessible resources for KAGRA do not provide comprehensive information on the design and implementation of its electrical wiring. Table 3.5 summarizes the electrical instruments in the KAGRA payload. Additionally, Figure 3.12 serves as a schematic representation of the KAGRA payload, outlining its main components—platform, marionette,

Figure 3.12: Schematic representation of KAGRA payload, illustrating the main structural components and key instrumentation (Information on the temperature of platform and marionette is not available).

intermediate mass, test mass, and their associated recoil masses: marionette-recoil mass (MRM), intermediate mass-recoil mass (IMRM), and test mass-recoil mass (TMRM), including the known, applied instrumentation. The key functional instruments, such as the moving mass system, reflective photo sensors, coils, and magnets, are listed in the legend. The heat link connections between stages and the connection to the HLVIS are also illustrated. Table A.1 in the appendix includes the schematic by providing a structured and comprehensive summary of the payload instrumentation and the respective available data.

Table 3.5: Overview of instruments in the payload of KAGRA, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, intermediate mass, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management).

Purpose of Use	Platform	Marionette	Intermediate Mass	Test Mass
Displacement Measurement	• -	• 6 reflective photo sensors (each sensor has 2 photodiodes and 1 LED)	• 6 reflective photo sensors	• -
Position Adjustment	• Moving mass system (with stepper motor)	• Moving mass system	• 6 coils	• 4 coils
Thermal and Optical Management	• Cernox temperature sensors	• Cernox temperature sensors	• Cernox temperature sensors	• Cernox temperature sensors • instrumented baffle

3.4 The Einstein Telescope (ET)

The ET is a third-generation gravitational wave detector, currently under development and is planned to be built underground to reduce seismic noise [12]. Unlike existing L-shaped interferometers, like AdV+, ET is planned to be a triangular-shaped Michelson-based detector, with two interferometers on each corner, establishing a xylophone design as shown in Figure 3.13 [2]. In order to reach higher sensitivity at lower frequency, ET's interferometers will have 10 km long arms and include cryogenic test masses [88]. The ET will include low-frequency (3 Hz to 30 Hz, ET-LF) cryogenic interferometers with high-frequency (30 Hz to 10 kHz, ET-HF) room-temperature interferometers [13]. In January 2025, investigations of the deeper soil layers commenced in the Belgian and Dutch candidate sites for the Einstein Telescope. Researchers are using vibration-based sensors to map the subsurface structure and determine the suitability for hosting the underground observatory, which will be built at depth to reduce seismic disturbances. [19, 89]

In order to extend ET's detection bandwidth into the low-frequency range, advanced seismic attenuation systems and cryogenic operation are required. A comprehensive study conducted as part of the 2011 ET Conceptual Design concluded

that the optimal solution should follow the Virgo SA design as baseline, which is described in Chapter 3.2. However, the final design is still under discussion to ensure compatibility with ET requirements. This involves extending the SA length to 17 m while maintaining the same number of filters. [11] A schematic of the SA design is presented in Figure 3.14a.

The input- and end-mirrors of ET-LF will be housed in cryostats to reduce thermal noise, similar to the approach used in KAGRA (as presented in Chapter 3.3). The ET adopts the payload of AdV+ as baseline design, which is described in Section 3.2.1, with adjustments made for cryogenic operation. The entire payload of ET-LF will be housed in the lower section of the vacuum tower. The base of the vacuum tower functions as a cryostat equipped with two thermal shields: the inner layer maintains a temperature of 5 K, while the outer layer serves as an intermediate-temperature shield at 80 K, as shown in Figure 3.14b. [11]

3.4.1 Cryogenic Payload in the low-frequency interferometer of ET

This thesis will use the baseline design for the cryogenic ET-LF payload and the cooling concepts, conducted in [13]. The payload design is based on AdV+, consisting of platform, marionette and test mass, with an actuator cage as the reaction mass, as shown in Figure 3.15.

Two cooling concepts have been proposed for the ET-LF cryogenic payload. The first follows the KAGRA approach, utilizing aluminum heat links but incorporating a monolithic suspension for the marionette, made of sapphire. To meet the high sensitivity requirements of ET, the heat links must be connected to the platform rather than the marionette, as cooling bars introduce vibrations. Since the marionette is positioned closer to the test mass, directly attaching the heat links to it would increase the risk of vibration transfer. Instead, the heat links are first connected to the platform. This approach differs from the design used in KAGRA, where the heat links from the cooling bars are directly connected to the marionette first (cf. Subsection 3.3.1). The second, a novel concept, proposed from the KKT-group at KIT, is based on helium cooling, where heat extraction is achieved through superfluid helium (He-II) within the so-called marionette suspension tube, which is made of titanium. [13] The design proposed in this work for the electrical instruments to be used in the cryogenic payload of ET-LF is based on a detailed comparison of the payload designs and components of KAGRA and AdV+, incorporating insights from both systems to address the specific requirements of ET.

Figure 3.13: Interferometer configuration of ET, highlighting the xylophone design [10]

Figure 3.14: Scheme of the SA (a) [11] with the payload housed in the cryostat (b) [12]

Figure 3.15: Baseline design of the cryogenic payload of ET, including platform, marionette, test mass (mirror) and actuator cage [13]

Figure 3.16: Schematic of the ET-LF cryogenic payload design proposal for electrical instruments, including buffer elements and main components.

Table 3.6: Overview of instruments in the proposed ET-LF cryogenic payload design, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal and optical management). Items denoted by * are buffer instruments.

Purpose of Use	Platform	Marionette	Test Mass
Displacement Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 Piezo sensors • *6 LVDTs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 reflective photo sensors (each consists of 1 LED and 2 photodiodes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 reflective photo sensors
Position Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 stepper motors for rotating • 2 stepper motors for moving mass system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 coils • 2 stepper motors for moving mass system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 coils • *picomotors for mirror positioning
Thermal and Optical Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 Cernox temperature sensors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Cernox temperature sensors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Cernox temperature sensors • instrumented baffle • *1 compensation plate with 2 picomotors

3.4.1.1 Platform

The platform is suspended from the room-temperature SA, and is the first component of the cryogenic payload. The platform suspends the marionette with a single suspension and the actuator cage with three suspensions. The temperature of the platform is expected to be between 2 K and 13 K (based on the proposed cooling concepts [13]), hence, this requires the electrical instruments to be cryogenic com-

patible. LVDTs are used as displacement sensors in AdV+, however, the cryogenic compatibility of LVDTs has not been verified [23]. Therefore, the reflective photo sensors of KAGRA could be adapted onto the platform of the ET-LF payload as displacement measuring sensors. As in all interferometric gravitational wave detectors, a moving mass system is essential for adjusting the center of gravity of payload parts (see Chapter 3.1.1). Both KAGRA and AdV+ implemented moving mass systems with stepper motors for this purpose. KAGRA has proven that their commercially available stepper motors can function successfully at cryogenic temperatures. While KAGRA also implements a cryogenic approach similar to ET-LF, the available information on its stepper motor configuration and position adjustment instrumentation for the platform is limited (cf. Subsection 3.3.1.1). Therefore, AdV+ serves as a more reliable baseline for this study. In conclusion, following the AdV+ design (see Subsection 3.2.1.1), 2 stepper motors could be applied to rotate the platform with respect to SA's lowest stage and other parts of the payload, while 2 additional stepper motors should be used as a part of moving mass system.

3.4.1.2 Marionette

The marionette adjusts the position of the mirror in the test mass with four monocrystalline silicon suspension fibers. The marionette's temperature is anticipated to range between 2 K and 17 K (based on the proposed cooling concepts [13]). Reflective photo sensors as in KAGRA could be utilized for the displacement measurement of the marionette. This suggests that 6 reflective photo sensors, consisting of a total of 12 photodiodes and 6 LEDs (cf. Figure 3.11a), can be integrated into the marionette of ET. The marionettes of KAGRA and AdV+ incorporate coil-magnet pairs for the actuation. The coils should be mounted on the actuator cage, while the respective magnets should be fixed to the marionette. In addition KAGRA implemented the moving mass system with stepper motors to the marionette. Hence, 2 stepper motors and 6 coil-magnet pairs should serve as position adjustment instruments for the marionette of ET.

3.4.1.3 Test Mass

The mirror and its suspension wires will consist of monocrystalline silicon or sapphire. The mirror's temperature is expected to range between 15 K and 20 K as a result of laser power. AdV+ features instrumented baffles with photodiodes positioned in front of its mirror. KAGRA also employs baffles; however, the baffles are not a part of the payload but still located within the cryostat. Additionally, it is unclear whether the baffles of KAGRA include photodiodes, although they are utilized in the marionette and intermediate mass of KAGRA. Based on these approaches, ET could integrate instrumented baffles equipped with 6 reflective photo sensors, similar to those utilized in KAGRA's marionette and intermediate mass. To adjust the position of the mirror stage, both detectors use coil-magnet pairs, indicating that 4 coils could be attached to the actuator cage, with the magnets on the mirror. In order to mitigate disturbances in the optical path caused by the changing refractive index of the mirror, resulting from heating due to the laser, AdV+ implemented ring heaters to maintain a uniform temperature across the mirror. While this phenomenon could also be present in ET, its impact is expected to be marginal due to the continuous cooling of the mirror. Since a ring heater cannot be implemented without compromising cryogenic operation, further R&D may be required to evaluate and address any potential alternatives. Scattered light is a common issue in nearly all gravitational wave detectors [18]. To address this, AdV+ implemented

compensation plates placed in front of the input-mirrors, with picomotors to adjust their position. Picomotors are available with proven compatibility at cryogenic temperatures [23]. Therefore, a compensation plate with 2 picomotors will be included in the design proposal as buffer to address potential scattered light issues. In order to measure the temperature of each stage, calibrated Cernox temperature sensors must also be implemented.

The selected instruments for the ET-LF cryogenic payload are based on the designs of AdV+ and KAGRA. These choices ensure compatibility with the cryogenic environment while maintaining precision in displacement measurement, position adjustment, and thermal and optical management. Table 3.6 and Figure 3.16 provide an overview of the selected components and their distribution within the payload.

4. Optimization of electrical wiring for cryogenic applications

This chapter presents the optimization methodology for parasitic heat load minimization in electrical wires for application in cryogenic ambience, followed by a detailed analysis and optimization of the electrical wires of GRAVITHELIUM test cryostat. The focus is on minimizing heat load on the cold end while maintaining electrical performance. The methodology is developed based on established design principles, considering material selection, geometric configurations, and operational constraints to achieve minimum heat load, as outlined in Chapter 2.

4.1 Optimization methodology

The wire dimension optimization is carried out in a sequential manner, where the diameter is optimized first, followed by the adjustment of length. This approach is chosen because the diameter influences the governing equations, Joule heat (Eq. 2.1) and conductive heat load 2.4, by two orders of magnitude more than the length. In particular, Joule heat is inversely proportional to the cross-sectional area A , which scales with d^2 , whereas the conductive heat load at the cold end is directly proportional to A and therefore also to d^2 . Optimizing the length before finalizing the diameter would lead to higher cold end heat load, as decreasing the diameter after increasing the length could result in excessive Joule heat. By first determining the optimal diameter under the given constraints, the length can then be adjusted accordingly to further minimize the cold end heat load.

To determine the minimum allowable diameter d_{\min} and maximum allowable length L_{\max} , the limiting criterion, where the overall Joule heat $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ (Eq. 2.14) does not exceed the conductive heat load on the warm end \dot{Q}_h (Eq. 2.15), is defined. This limiting condition is based on the comparison between the constant input current I_0 and optimal current I_{opt} , which changes with variations in diameter, length or temperature range. The optimal current is calculated with the shape factor S from Eq. 2.30:

$$I_{\text{opt}} = \frac{S \cdot A_0}{L_0} = \frac{S \cdot \pi \cdot d_0^2}{4 \cdot L_0} \quad (4.1)$$

The comparison between I_{opt} and I_0 allows the identification of the correlation between the current values and the limiting criterion: For the case, where $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ is less than \dot{Q}_{h} , I_{opt} is significantly larger than I_0 . As the diameter is decreased, $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ increases while I_{opt} decreases. Once I_{opt} becomes smaller than I_0 , \dot{Q}_{h} changes sign, meaning that the wire is overheating. Prior to this point, $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ remains slightly smaller or equal to \dot{Q}_{h} , as I_{opt} approaches I_0 . Therefore, it is concluded, that the case, where $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ does not exceed but is close in value to \dot{Q}_{h} , gives the optimum diameter. Hence, this serves as the chosen limiting criterion. The same reasoning applies when the length is increased.

It is important to note that the calculation of I_{opt} and its comparison to I_0 are not a part of the optimization algorithm. However, the comparison was performed for an exemplary case in order to analyze underlying patterns and establish the limiting criterion accordingly, which is presented in the following. Since the correlation between the current values and the limiting criterion is independent of parameter variations, and it remains valid under all conditions, including I_{opt} in the algorithm is not necessary. Instead, comparing the values of \dot{Q}_{h} and $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ according to the limiting criterion is sufficient to determine the optimized parameters.

Figure 4.1 presents a flowchart summarizing the step-by-step process of the optimization methodology. The algorithm is implemented in Wolfram-Mathematica to iteratively determine the optimal wire dimensions. The material properties for the calculations are obtained from CryoComp [14].

The process begins by defining input parameters (I_0 , d_0 , L_0 , T_c and T_h). These parameters are defined based on data sheets for electrical instruments or, if unavailable, estimated based on general standards. From these set of parameters, the optimization is only applied to the diameter and length, whereas the temperature and current values remain constant throughout the whole process. Afterwards, the governing equations (Eq. 2.11, 2.14, 2.15, 2.16) and boundary conditions 2.12 and 2.13 are defined, before solving the differential equation 2.11. The solution of the differential equation gives the temperature distribution $T(x)$. Once \dot{Q}_{c} , \dot{Q}_{h} , and $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ are calculated with $T(x)$, the optimization proceeds in a sequential manner. First, the length is set as constant. Afterwards, the wire diameter is iteratively reduced until the limiting criterion—where $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ does not exceed \dot{Q}_{h} —is met. At the end of this step, the minimum allowable diameter, d_{min} , is identified.

Next, the length is increased while keeping d_{min} and I_0 constant, checking the limiting criterion at every iteration to further minimize \dot{Q}_{c} . The maximum allowable length, L_{max} , is obtained at the end of this process, thereby completing the optimization with the values d_{min} and L_{max} . While L_{max} is primarily determined based on the limiting criterion, practical constraints such as spatial limitations of the application may also affect the determination. These aspects are further discussed in Chapter 5.

To enhance clarity, an exemplary calculation is provided. This calculation illustrates the approach step by step, providing a concrete application of the methodology. Additionally, the underlying principles of the limiting criterion are explained, by showing the correlation of I_0 and I_{opt} with $\dot{Q}_{\text{I,total}}$ and \dot{Q}_{h} .

For simplicity, the electrical wires are modeled as homogeneous cylindrical conductors, with temperature variations considered only along their axial direction, the length L . Each wire starts at a cold temperature T_c and reaches a warm temperature T_h . Table 4.1 shows the dimensions and properties of the exemplary wire.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart of the optimization algorithm

The goal of the optimization is to minimize the parasitic heat load on the cold end of the wire \dot{Q}_c , by adjusting the dimensions of the wire. Given that the algorithm for the optimization is an iterative process, a series of input parameters need to be defined. The dimensions and properties of the exemplary wire in Table 4.1 are set as input parameters (I_0 , d_0 , L_0 , T_c and T_h).

The temperature distribution of the wire $T(x)$ can be obtained by solving the differential equation 2.11 with the boundary conditions, respectively for the warm end 2.12 and cold end 2.13. The heat load on cold end \dot{Q}_c and warm end \dot{Q}_h , as well as overall Joule heat $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ can be calculated with the equations 2.16, 2.15, 2.14 by applying $T(x)$. Additionally, the optimal current I_{opt} can be determined with the equation 4.1.

Table 4.2 shows the calculated values of the exemplary wire without an optimization. It is important to note that due to the defined coordinates in the system, depicted in Figure 2.3, \dot{Q}_c and \dot{Q}_h are negative. However, given that $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ is calculated integrally for the total length of the wire, its value is positive. In other words, the negative sign of \dot{Q}_c and \dot{Q}_h indicates only the direction of the conductive heat flow. Moreover, it can be observed from the Tables 4.1 and 4.2 that I_{opt} is nearly four times greater than I_0 before the optimization, indicating that the diameter of the wire can be decreased to minimize \dot{Q}_c .

The diameter is varied in AWG sizes. The parameters I_0 , L_0 , T_c and T_h are kept constant to observe the effect of diameter reduction. The value of S also remains constant, as it depends solely on the material properties and temperature range (cf. Eq. 2.30).

Table 4.3 shows the results of diameter variation. As the diameter decreases, the absolute values of \dot{Q}_c and \dot{Q}_h are reduced, which is favorable; however, this also results in an increase in $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$. The rationale is that $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ is inversely proportional to the diameter, whereas \dot{Q}_c and \dot{Q}_h , calculated using Fourier's law 2.4, are directly proportional to it.

Along with the absolute values of \dot{Q}_c and \dot{Q}_h , I_{opt} also decreases, as the diameter decreases. Once it falls below the given input current I_0 —at 36 AWG in this case— \dot{Q}_h changes sign and becomes positive. This indicates that the wire is overheating and has exceeded its ampacity limit, a condition that must be avoided to ensure safe operation (cf. Section 2.2). Consequently, I_{opt} must always remain above

Table 4.1: Dimension and properties of an exemplary wire

Material	AWG	d_0	L_0	I_0	T_c	T_h
[-]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[A]	[K]	[K]
Copper (RRR = 50)	30	0.2546	50	1.0	60	300

Table 4.2: Results of the exemplary wire without an optimization

\dot{Q}_c	\dot{Q}_h	$\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$	S	I_{opt}
[W]	[W]	[W]	[A m ⁻¹]	[A]
-0.10667	-0.09746	0.00905	$3.75468 \cdot 10^6$	3.83507

Table 4.3: Results of wire diameter variation

AWG	d	L_0	\dot{Q}_c	\dot{Q}_h	$\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$	I_{opt}	I_0
[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[W]	[W]	[W]	[A]	[A]
30	0.2546	50	-0.10667	-0.09746	0.00905	3.83507	1.0
31	0.2268	50	-0.08608	-0.07434	0.01151	3.03910	1.0
32	0.2019	50	-0.07021	-0.05541	0.01475	2.40656	1.0
33	0.1798	50	-0.05836	-0.03932	0.01896	1.91090	1.0
34	0.1601	50	-0.04970	-0.02476	0.02486	1.50985	1.0
35	0.1426	50	-0.04456	-0.01155	0.03300	1.20610	1.0
36	0.1270	50	-0.04322	+0.00372	0.04689	0.95126	1.0

I_0 . Therefore, the smallest diameter, where I_{opt} is larger than I_0 , is defined as the critical diameter (35 AWG in this case). This diameter is the smallest diameter that can carry the current I_0 without overheating.

While 35 AWG is technically applicable, it may provide limited tolerance to parameter variations. To introduce a safety margin, the final selection of the diameter is refined by ensuring that $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ remains smaller than the absolute value of \dot{Q}_h . This safety margin was derived from an observation of a consistent pattern across different cases: The next biggest diameter, where I_{opt} is higher than I_0 , results in an absolute value of \dot{Q}_h larger than $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$. This diameter represents the optimized, smallest feasible diameter d_{min} , which is chosen as the final selection. However, this pattern is not immediately observed at the next bigger diameter after the critical diameter, but rather at the second next bigger one, as in the presented exemplary case: 35 AWG is the critical diameter, as it is increased to 34AWG, the absolute value of \dot{Q}_h still remains smaller than $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$. Finally, 33 AWG satisfies the limiting criterion, as the absolute value of \dot{Q}_h is larger than $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$. For this case, d_{min} is at 33 AWG, instead of 34 AWG. This is not necessarily a drawback but rather reinforces the reliability of the limiting criterion, ensuring universal validation.

This concludes the definition of the limiting criterion, that $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ must remain lower than the absolute value of \dot{Q}_h . This criterion guarantees both safe conduction of I_0 and minimum \dot{Q}_c .

After the determination of d_{min} , the influence of wire length is assessed while keeping d_{min} constant at 33 AWG. As the Fourier's law 2.4 suggest, increasing the length would result in a decrease of \dot{Q}_c .

Table 4.4 presents the results of the length variation, where, for the sake of simplicity, results are shown in absolute values since the sign change in the case of overheating has already been demonstrated. From this point onward, the heat load results in this thesis will be presented as absolute values. This does not affect the interpretation of the results, as the relative differences and trends remain unchanged.

From the Table 4.4, it can be observed that increasing the length reduces \dot{Q}_h , \dot{Q}_c and I_{opt} . In contrast, $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ increases with the increasing L . The rationale is that $\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$ exhibits a direct proportionality to the wire length, whereas \dot{Q}_h and \dot{Q}_c an inverse proportionality. The length can be increased until the predefined limiting criterion is met. Based on this consideration, a length of 63 mm is identified as the optimal design choice.

Table 4.4: Results of wire length variation

AWG	d_{\min}	L	\dot{Q}_c	\dot{Q}_h	$\dot{Q}_{I,\text{total}}$	I_{opt}	I_0
[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[W]	[W]	[W]	[A]	[A]
33	0.1798	50	0.05836	0.03932	0.01896	1.91090	1.0
33	0.1798	55	0.05445	0.03331	0.02111	1.73718	1.0
33	0.1798	60	0.05130	0.02794	0.02332	1.59242	1.0
33	0.1798	61	0.05081	0.02700	0.02381	1.56631	1.0
33	0.1798	62	0.05030	0.02599	0.02425	1.54105	1.0
33	0.1798	63	0.04980	0.02501	0.02471	1.49289	1.0

Table 4.5: Comparison of results for the initial design and optimized design (first row: initial design, second row: optimized design)

Material	T_c	T_h	AWG	d	L	I	\dot{Q}_c
[-]	[K]	[K]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[A]	[W]
Copper (RRR = 50)	60	300	30	0.2546	50	1.0	0.10667
Copper (RRR = 50)	60	300	33	0.1798	63	1.0	0.04980

Table 4.5 presents a comparison between the initial and optimized wire configurations. The initial design, featuring an AWG size of 30, a diameter of 0.2546 mm (d_0), and a length of 50 mm (L_0), resulted in a \dot{Q}_c value of 0.11 W. After optimization, the wire parameters were adjusted to an AWG size of 33, a diameter of 0.1798 mm (d_{\min}), and a length of 63 mm (L_{\max}). The optimization significantly reduced the parasitic heat load on the cold end to 0.05 W, corresponding to a 55% reduction.

4.2 Electrical wiring for the GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat

In this section, the developed optimization methodology explained in Section 4.1 is applied to the electrical wiring system in GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat (GR). The section first provides an overview of GR, including its key components and instrumentation. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the electrical wiring for the instruments. Finally, the results of the optimization are presented, demonstrating how the methodology refines the wiring design to minimize parasitic heat load.

4.2.1 GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat

The GR is designed as a dedicated test facility for investigating the mechanical dissipation in cryogenic payload suspensions, which are crucial components in the ET-LF payload [90]. In the ET-LF payload, suspension thermal noise is one of the dominant noise sources, significantly affecting sensitivity below 10 Hz. To mitigate this, the payload suspensions must operate at cryogenic temperatures and be constructed from materials with high thermal conductivity and low mechanical dissipation [18]. However, the dissipative behavior of these suspensions cannot be accurately simulated and must instead be defined via the so-called quality factor [90].

GR enables these studies by providing a controlled cryogenic environment where the quality factor of suspension materials can be determined via ring-down measurements. The facility allows for testing different suspension geometries and materials, including monolithic silicon and sapphire fibers as well as helium-II-filled titanium tubes. These experiments contribute to optimizing suspension designs for the ET-LF payload. [90]

The cryostat operates in a vacuum environment and utilizes a cryocooler-based cooling to reach temperatures below 5 K. The cryostat includes a thermalization shield at 60 K, which helps reduce radiative heat transfer. The test samples are mounted within a test chamber, cooled down to 5 K. In addition, a vibration isolation stage minimizes external disturbances. [90]

The ring-down method is used to measure the quality factor of a sample by analyzing its natural oscillations. The sample is first excited to oscillate, after which the exciter is turned off, and the amplitude decay is recorded. The key instruments required for this method include an exciter to induce oscillations and a shadow meter to measure the decay over time. [90, 91]

The exciter is a comb-capacitor that receives an oscillating current to generate a magnetic field, which in turn causes vibrations in the sample. These vibrations make the sample oscillate, and its motion is detected by an optical system known as a shadow meter. The shadow meter consists of one calibrated laser as a light source and a laser diode that detect variations in shadow cast on the sample from the laser. Changes in the light intensity correlate with the vibration or displacement of the sample, allowing precise measurement of the oscillation decay. To transmit the shadow meter's response, coaxial cables (model Type-SC from Lakeshore Cryotronics [92]) will be utilized. [90]

Additionally stepper motors (model D35.1 UHV from Arun Microelectronics [93]) will be used in the experimental setup to adjust the positioning of the shadow meter components involved in the measurement process. Moreover, the setup includes an additional laser, utilized for the calibrated helium-II tests and various Cernox sensors for measuring the temperature. [90]

Within the scope of this work, the following main instruments are analyzed and their wires optimized: 2 lasers, 2 exciters and 3 stepper motors. Given that the Type-SC cables are commercial products, they will not undergo the optimization process. However, their contribution to the total heat load will be calculated and presented alongside other instruments.

The electrical wiring follows a gradual thermalization process as the temperature descends from room temperature down to the cryogenic environment, as illustrated in Figure 4.2a. The electrical wiring starts at room temperature (300 K) in an atmospheric environment and enters the vacuum region through a feedthrough. Inside the vacuum, the wires extend downward and are soldered onto a vacuum plug assembly, where soldered capillaries ensure stable electrical contacts. The wiring then reaches the 60 K stage via additional plugs as depicted in Figure 4.2a, where thermalization in order to reduce parasitic heat conduction further down the cryostat occurs. At this point, the wires remain inside the vacuum and continue towards the 5 K stage, where they pass through another vacuum plug before reaching the final feedthrough at 5 K.

This gradual thermalization ensures that heat is progressively extracted at intermediate thermalization points, minimizing parasitic heat load while maintaining electrical stability in the cryogenic environment.

Figure 4.2: The schematic of the Cernox wiring and feedthroughs with thermalization stages (a) and the schematic of GRAVITHELIUM test cryostat (b) *courtesy of X. Korovesi and M. Stamm*

Table 4.6: Input parameters for the electrical wiring of GRAVITHELIUM instruments.

Input	Instrument Information		Electrical Wiring Parameters				
	Type	Total Wires	AWG	d_0 [mm]	L_0 [mm]	I_0 [mA]	Material
(1)	2 Lasers	4	36	0.1270	50	100	Copper
(2)	2 Exciters	4	24	0.5106	50	10	Manganin
(3)	3 Stepper Motors	12	22	0.6438	50	1000	Copper
(4)	2 Type-SC Cables	65	50	0.0251	60	10	Copper

4.2.2 Optimization

The optimization of the electrical wires is based on the methodology explained in Section 4.1. Based on the instruments and the thermalization presented in Subsection 4.2.1, the input parameters for the optimization process can be defined. Since the algorithm considers one temperature range at a time, the optimization will first be performed for the section between 300 K and 60 K, followed by the section between 60 K and 5 K.

Table 4.6 presents the input parameters for the electrical wiring of the GRAVITHELIUM instruments. For ease of reference, the inputs are numbered from 1 to 4. This numbering system is intended to simplify the comparison of input data and their results across the tables. The parameter d_0 for each input is determined based on technical datasheets or standard electrical specifications, whereas L_0 values are assumptions. Each laser and exciter requires 2 wires per instrument, while each

stepper motor is connected via 4 wires, leading to 4, 4, and 12 wires, respectively. The stepper motors have 3 additional wires each, which are used for temperature measuring. However, they are assumed to be not necessary in this scope of work. Additionally, the properties of the Type-SC are presented in Table 4.6. The Type SC cable consists of 65 strands of 50 AWG wires. Each wire of the Type-SC cable has an assumed length of 60 mm. The presented current values (I_0) are determined based on the electrical requirements of each instrument, either from manufacturer datasheets or standard operating conditions.

The material used for wiring depends on the application. Copper (RRR = 50) is chosen for the laser and stepper motors due to its low electrical resistivity, as this material property is needed to conduct high currents without overheating. For the stepper motor wires, copper is specifically provided by the manufacturer [93]. The copper wires of the Type-SC cable are insulated with Teflon. Nonetheless, only the copper wires will be assessed in this scope of work. Moreover, manganin is used for the exciter wires. Since the exciter only receives 10 mA, low electrical resistivity is not a primary consideration. In addition, manganin's lower thermal conductivity compared to copper helps to reduce the parasitic heat load. The parameters d_0 and L_0 of inputs 1, 2 and 3 serve as the starting point for the optimization process. The temperature and current values remain constant throughout the entire optimization. In addition, the parasitic heat load of the Type-SC cables will be calculated and presented in the following tables.

For the evaluation of the results, the calculated heat load values before an optimization will be presented first, followed by the optimized results for each of the two temperature ranges, which are denoted with 300 K \rightarrow 60 K and 60 K \rightarrow 5 K. To determine the total heat load on the cold end for both temperature ranges, the heat load of a single wire for each input is first calculated. These values are then multiplied by the total number of wires corresponding to each input. Finally, the resulting heat load contributions from all inputs are summed, resulting the total heat load at the cold end.

Table 4.7 shows \dot{Q}_c values obtained from the input parameters before the optimization. The total heat load at the 60 K thermalization stage sums to 8.14 W, whereas at 5 K, the total heat load amounts to 4.68 W. Among the three instrument types, input (3), corresponding to the stepper motors, results in the highest parasitic heat load due to its higher current value.

Table 4.7: Input results showing cold end heat loads.

Input	300 K \rightarrow 60 K		60 K \rightarrow 5 K	
	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]
(1)	0.02580	0.10319	0.01457	0.05827
(2)	0.01575	0.06300	0.00153	0.00613
(3)	0.66037	7.92446	0.38326	4.59912
(4)	0.00082	0.05306	0.00027	0.01726
Total	–	8.14371	–	4.68078

In contrast, the exciters (input 2) generate the lowest contribution to the overall heat load. These results form the basis for evaluating how much heat can be reduced through the optimization.

Tables 4.8 and 4.9 summarize the optimized cold end heat loads for the two temperature ranges: 300 K \rightarrow 60 K and 60 K \rightarrow 5 K. The results include the minimum wire diameter (d_{\min}), the corresponding AWG size, the maximum wire length (L_{\max}), and the conductive heat load per wire (\dot{Q}_c). Additionally, the total heat load contribution from all wires of each input type is presented, followed by the total heat load on the thermalization stages in the last row of each table.

A comparison between instrument types (1) and (2) in Table 4.8 reveals that the heat load per wire for type (1) is greater than that of type (2), despite its smaller diameter. This difference arises because type (2) wires carry less current and are composed of manganin. Although manganin has a higher electrical resistivity compared to copper, its lower thermal conductivity results in a lower heat load. The same trend is observed in the second temperature range, in Table 4.9.

Table 4.8: Optimized results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the first temperature range.

Input	300 K \rightarrow 60 K				
	AWG [-]	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]
(1)	43	0.0564	62	0.00497	0.01989
(2)	36	0.1270	59	0.00022	0.00387
(3)	33	0.1798	63	0.04974	0.59681
(4)	–	–	–	0.00082	0.05306
Total	–	–	–	–	0.67364

Table 4.9: Optimized results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the second temperature range.

Input	60 K \rightarrow 5 K				
	AWG [-]	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]
(1)	48	0.0316	60	0.00078	0.00312
(2)	33	0.1798	50	0.00024	0.00096
(3)	38	0.1007	60	0.00790	0.09483
(4)	–	–	–	0.00027	0.01726
Total	–	–	–	–	0.11617

Figure 4.3: Heat load distribution across all inputs for optimized values. The left chart represents the distribution from 300 K to 60 K, while the right chart shows the distribution from 60 K to 5 K.

For a visual comparison, Figure 4.3 shows the heat distribution from each input at each temperature range. Despite the optimization, type (3) wires contribute the highest heat load with approximately 89% between 300 K and 60 K, due to their higher current requirement. In contrast, in the 60 K → 5 K range, input (4) dominates with 40%, while (3) contributes 30%. This occurs because (4) is a commercial product and remains unoptimized, whereas (3) undergoes optimization. This suggests that while (4) performs well at higher temperatures with low parasitic heat load, at lower temperatures, it should either be optimized or replaced with a more suitable commercial solution, as a 10 mA input should not contribute more parasitic heat load than a 1.0 A input.

Overall, the minimum total heat load at the cold end is 0.67 W at 60 K and 0.12 W at 5 K. The comparison between the results in Table 4.7 and the results after the optimization in Tables 4.8 and 4.9 indicates a total parasitic heat reduction of 91.8% at 60 K and 97.4% at 5 K, which is a marginal reduction.

However, the optimized diameters correspond to significantly smaller sizes (i.e., higher AWG numbers), which are not commercially available. In particular, d_{\min} for input (1) is only 0.06 mm and 0.03 mm for each temperature range, respectively. The thinnest commercially available copper wire is 38 AWG (0.1007 mm). Therefore, any optimized diameters smaller than this must be set at 38 AWG to achieve a feasible design. Since increasing the wire diameter leads to higher heat loads, the wire length should be maximized wherever possible to compensate.

Tables 4.10 and 4.11 present the achievable results after adjusting the wire diameters to the smallest commercially available sizes. Among the three instrument types, only type (1) wires were below the available size range and were therefore increased to 38 AWG. This adjustment leads to a slight increase in the total parasitic heat load, namely, 0.7 W at 60 K, and 0.12 W at 5 K. Specifically, at 60 K, the total heat

load is increased by 5% and at 5 K by 17%. The higher percentage increase at 5 K compared to 60 K is because when both optimized diameters at each temperature range are increased to the same commercially available size (0.1007 mm), the relative increase is more significant at 5 K compared to 60 K. This is because the optimized diameter at 5 K (0.03 mm) undergoes a proportionally larger increase than at 60 K (0.06 mm). As a result, the enforced diameter increase leads to a greater increase in parasitic heat load at 5 K. The increase in diameter to commercially available size ensures a feasible design while still resulting in a lower parasitic heat load than the initial design.

Table 4.10: Achievable results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the first temperature range.

Input	300 K \rightarrow 60 K				
	AWG [-]	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]
(1)	38	0.1007	70	0.01182	0.04727
(2)	36	0.1270	59	0.00022	0.00387
(3)	33	0.1798	63	0.04974	0.59681
(4)	–	–	–	0.00082	0.05306
Total	–	–	–	–	0.70101

Table 4.11: Achievable results showing cold end heat loads and wire dimensions for the second temperature range.

Input	60 K \rightarrow 5 K				
	AWG [-]	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]
(1)	38	0.1007	70	0.00663	0.02651
(2)	33	0.1798	50	0.00024	0.00096
(3)	38	0.1007	60	0.00790	0.09483
(4)	–	–	–	0.00027	0.01726
Total	–	–	–	–	0.13955

5. Optimization of electrical wiring for the ET

This chapter presents an optimization study of the electrical wires entering the ET-LF cryostat from the upper part, which are required for the cryogenic payload instrumentation, with the goal of minimizing their parasitic heat load. First the system boundaries conditions are defined, including the cryostat structure, followed by an introduction to the input parameters relevant to the electrical wires.

In this thesis, two different cooling concepts of the payload are analyzed: monolithic cooling, where the payload components are cooled with heat links made out of aluminum, and helium-based cooling, which utilizes helium as the primary cooling medium in a marionette suspension tube (see Section 3.4.1). Each of these concepts is further divided into three cases: one without wire thermalization, one with a wire thermalization at 80 K, and one with wire thermalization at both 80 K and 5 K to further reduce the parasitic heat load. In total, six thermal analysis cases for the electrical wires are examined to determine their impact on the parasitic heat load to the payload. Additionally, a material selection study is conducted for one selected thermal analysis case to assess the feasibility of alternative materials in reducing the total parasitic heat load. The final section of this chapter provides a comparative analysis of all cases to evaluate their impact on the ET-LF payload.

5.1 System definition and input parameters

The cryostat structure and the suspension wires follow the ET-LF cryogenic payload design proposed in [13]. In the cryostat, three temperature stages are present, as depicted in Figure 5.1: The outermost boundary, indicated in gray, represents the 300 K outer vessel, which acts as the starting point for electrical wires. The first wire thermalization at 80 K (green) is located after the outer boundary. This is followed with the next layer, which is the second wire thermalization at 5 K (blue). The electrical wires are assumed to be housed in a metal tube from 300 K to 5 K, entering the cryostat from the upper part of the SA, similar to the configuration in AdV+ (cf. Subsection 3.2.1.4). After this point, the wires exit the metal tube to extend to their respective payload component.

Figure 5.1: Schematic representation of the distances between the cryostat and payload components, illustrating the thermalization stages at 80 K and 5 K.

Table 5.1 presents the input parameters for the electrical wiring of the payload instruments. The instrument types, their respective quantities, and wiring specifications are listed for the platform, marionette, and test mass, respectively. It is important to note that the instruments listed under marionette and test mass also include instruments that are mounted on their respective cage sections. The detailed information regarding the purpose of these instruments is provided in Section 3.4.1 and summarized in Table 3.6. The parameters d_0 and L_0 in Table 5.1 serve as the baseline for the optimization process, while the I_0 values remain constant for the entire optimization. The definition of the inputs d_0 , L_0 and I_0 is explained in the following.

To define the input length of the wires inside the cryostat, the spatial structure of the cryostat and the payload, as depicted in Figure 5.1, must be considered. The suspension wire lengths (1000 mm and 1200 mm) are based on the design presented in [13], whereas all other spatial distances are assumed values in Figure 5.1. Within this scope of work, it is assumed that the distances between the payload components define the minimum required length of the electrical wires. Since the distance from the outer vessel to the 80 K and from 80 K to 5 K is 100 mm each, the electrical wires must also have a length of 100 mm within both ranges. Beyond the wire thermalization at 5 K, the wire lengths are assumed based on the structural layout of the ET-LF payload. Since electrical wires inside the payload will not follow a perfectly straight path in their actual implementation, a certain amount of flexibility is necessary for installation. However, excessive wire length should be avoided to minimize parasitic heat load. As a balanced approach, the estimated wire lengths are set to reach the bottom of the platform and the marionette. In particular, the platform's body has a height of 250 mm, and since the total distance from the 5 K stage to the top of the platform is 250 mm, the electrical wires assigned to the

platform must have a length of 500 mm. The wires then extend further by 1000 mm, corresponding to the suspension wire length from the platform to the marionette. Consequently, the required length for the wires assigned to the marionette is 1500 mm. Lastly, the suspension wire length between the marionette and test mass is 1200 mm, resulting in a total length of 2700 mm to reach the respective section of the actuator cage for the test mass.

The current values (I_0) in Table 5.1 are determined based on technical datasheets or standard electrical specifications for each instrument in the payload. The initial wire diameter (d_0) and AWG values correspond to the assumed sizes before optimization. All wires are made of copper (RRR = 50), except for the Cernox wires, which are composed of phosphor bronze. Both material choices are based on established practical standards. Instruments denoted with * represent buffer instruments. The reasoning behind their designation as buffer instruments is discussed in Subsection 3.4.1.

Table 5.1: Input parameters for electrical wiring of payload instruments (All wires are made of copper (RRR = 50), except the phosphor bronze Cernox wires. Buffer instruments are denoted with *).

Input	Instrument Type	Instrument Quantity	Wire Quantity	Total Wires	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_0 [mm]	L_0 [mm]
Platform								
1	Piezo Actuator	3	2	6	100	31	0.2268	500
2	*LVDT	6	2	12	100	31	0.2268	500
3	Stepper Motor	4	4	16	1000	22	0.6438	500
4	Cernox	2	2	4	0.01	36	0.1270	500
Marionette								
5	Photodiode	12	2	24	10	35	0.1426	1500
6	LED	6	2	12	350	22	0.6438	1500
7	Stepper Motor	2	4	8	1000	22	0.6438	1500
8	Coil	6	4	12	9.4	37	0.1131	1500
9	Cernox	4	2	8	0.01	36	0.1270	1500
Test Mass								
10	Photodiode	12	2	24	10	35	0.1426	2700
11	LED	6	2	12	350	22	0.6438	2700
12	Coil	4	2	8	1.7	37	0.1131	2700
13	*Picomotor TM	2	4	8	10	35	0.1426	2700
14	*Picomotor CP	2	4	8	10	35	0.1426	2700
15	Cernox	4	2	8	0.01	36	0.1270	2700

Table 5.2: Overview of the six thermal analysis cases for the electrical wires with different payload cooling concepts and wire thermalization strategies.

Case	Cooling Concept	Thermal Path	T_{PF} [K]	T_{MA} [K]	T_{TM} [K]
1	Monolithic	300 K \rightarrow Payload	13	17	20
2	Monolithic	300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload	13	17	20
3	Monolithic	300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload	13	17	20
4	Helium (He-II)	300 K \rightarrow Payload	2	2	15
5	Helium (He-II)	300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload	2	2	15
6	Helium (He-II)	300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload	2	2	15

5.2 Cooling Concepts and Thermal Analysis Cases

Two different cooling concepts are considered for the ET-LF payload: monolithic cooling and helium-based cooling [13]. The necessity of cryogenic cooling, its impact on thermal noise, and the general cooling requirements for ET-LF payload have been discussed in Chapter 3. This section focuses on the implementation of the boundary conditions imposed from the cooling concepts into the optimization algorithm explained in Section 4.1.

In the monolithic cooling concept, a similar approach to the one implemented in KAGRA is utilized (see Section 3.3). Aluminum heat links are connected from the cooling bars to the platform first, and from there, they extend to the marionette and test mass. The suspension wires also provide thermal connection between the payload components. This cooling method results in the following expected temperatures: 13 K at the platform, 17 K at the marionette, and 20 K at the test mass. [13] To evaluate the impact of different thermalization strategies for the electrical wires, three thermal analysis cases are considered for the monolithic cooling concept. In the first case, no thermalization of the wires are present, meaning that the wires extend directly from 300 K to their respective payload parts. The second case introduces a wire thermalization at 80 K, where the wires first reach this intermediate temperature before continuing to the payload. Lastly, the third case includes an additional wire thermalization at 5 K, in addition to the 80 K, before the wires extend to their respective payload parts.

The helium-based cooling concept relies on a suspension tube filled with superfluid helium, between the platform and the marionette. Due to the exceptional thermal conductivity of superfluid helium, both the platform and marionette are expected to reach a temperature of 2 K. However, the test mass is expected to be 15 K. [13] Similar to the monolithic cooling concept, three thermalization strategies are considered for this cooling concept. In total, this results in six different cases, with three thermalization strategies for each of the two cooling concepts. It is important to note that for all cases the cage temperature is assumed to be identical to the corresponding payload part it surrounds.

Table 5.2 summarizes the six thermal analysis cases with different payload cooling concepts and wire thermalization strategies, summarizing the cases in thermal paths. The temperature values of each payload component correspond to the as-

summed temperatures depending on the cooling concept: T_{PF} denotes the platform temperature, T_{MA} represents the marionette temperature, and T_{TM} refers to the test mass temperature. The parasitic heat loads from each input listed in Table 5.1 are calculated and then optimized for each thermal analysis case.

5.3 Evaluation of the Thermal Analysis Cases

This section follows the same approach used in Subsection 4.2.2, where the results are evaluated in three stages, namely: First, the input results are calculated based on the initial wire parameters (all instruments, see Table 5.1). Afterwards, the optimized results are obtained by applying the optimization methodology to minimize the parasitic heat load, as explained in Section 4.1. Lastly, the achievable results are derived after applying commercially available wire sizes to ensure feasibility. The results for each case is presented in Tables 5.3 and 5.4. Additionally, the wire design results of the optimization, including optimal diameter and length, are provided in the appendix (A.2 - A.9).

Table 5.3: Comparison of total heat loads for Monolithic Cooling (Cases 1-3)

Case 1: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
To Platform (13 K)	1.8726	0.8994	0.9004
To Marionette (17 K)	0.8045	0.6355	0.6424
To Test Mass (20 K)	0.2757	0.2339	0.2360
Total to Payload	2.9528	1.7688	1.7787
Case 2: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
To Platform (13 K)	0.7717	0.2179	0.2180
To Marionette (17 K)	0.2924	0.1555	0.1600
To Test Mass (20 K)	0.1002	0.0582	0.0600
Total to Payload	1.1643	0.4311	0.4379
Case 3: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
From Platform (13 K)	0.0613	0.0436	0.04360
From Marionette (17 K)	0.0518	0.0458	0.0461
From Test Mass (20 K)	0.0216	0.0201	0.0203
80 K \rightarrow 5 K	12.2265	0.4187	0.9325
Total to 5 K	12.3612	0.5282	1.0425

Table 5.4: Comparison of total heat loads for Helium Cooling (Cases 4-6)

Case 4: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
To Platform (2 K)	1.9460	0.9027	0.9036
To Marionette (2 K)	0.8437	0.6340	0.6423
To Test Mass (15 K)	0.2851	0.2331	0.2356
Total to Payload	3.0748	1.7697	1.7816
Case 5: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
To Platform (2 K)	0.8426	0.2189	0.2190
To Marionette (2 K)	0.3390	0.1534	0.1599
To Test Mass (15 K)	0.1097	0.0564	0.0588
Total to Payload	1.2912	0.4287	0.4378
Case 6: Thermal Path: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload			
Payload Section	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Optimized [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]
To Platform (2 K)	0.0153	0.0148	0.0148
To Marionette (2 K)	0.0122	0.0109	0.0109
From Test Mass (15 K)	0.0151	0.0117	0.0118
80 K \rightarrow 5 K	12.2265	0.4187	0.9325
Total to 5 K	12.2415	0.4304	0.9443
Total to Payload	0.02755	0.02566	0.02566

A general trend across Tables 5.3 and 5.4 is that, the wires that are for the platform results in the highest parasitic heat load in comparison to the ones for the marionette and test mass. This is primarily due to the presence of multiple electrical instruments, such as stepper motors, which require significantly higher currents compared to other instruments (see Table 5.1). In order to evaluate the impact of different cases, each case is analyzed individually in the following.

Table 5.3 shows that Case 1, where no wire thermalization is present, results in the highest parasitic heat load (1.77 W), among the cases with monolithic cooling (Case 1-3). The results of Case 2 are lower than Case 1, as the wire thermalization at 80 K reduces the parasitic heat load to 0.43 W. Case 3 further extends this approach by incorporating thermalization at 5 K in addition to 80 K. This is highly beneficial for the payload, as no parasitic heat is transferred to the payload. Instead, the heat flows from the payload to the wire thermalization stage at 5 K, since the temperatures of all payload components are higher than 5 K. To reflect this difference, Table 5.3

uses the terms “to” and “from”. Accordingly, in Case 3, the total parasitic heat load at 5 K (0.53 W) is the sum of two contributions: the heat transferred from 80 K to 5 K and from the payload to 5 K.

After the evaluation of the Cases 1, 2, and 3, the analysis proceeds with Cases 4, 5, and 6 to assess the impact of helium-based cooling. The corresponding results are shown in Table 5.4. In Case 4 the total parasitic heat load is the highest among all cases, namely 1.78 W. This relies primarily on the wide the temperature range, spanning from 300 K to 2 K and 15 K, respectively. In Case 5, wire thermalization at 80 K is introduced, which reduces the parasitic heat load to 0.43 W. Finally, in Case 6, wire thermalization occurs both at 80 K and 5 K. The heat flows from 5 K to platform and marionette, respectively. In contrast, given the higher test mass temperature than 5 K, the heat flows from the test mass to 5 K. Consequently, Case 6 results in the lowest parasitic heat load to the payload (0.03 W) among all cases.

With the individual case analyses completed, the results of all cases are now compared with each other to assess the influence of different thermalization strategies and cooling concepts. Figure 5.2 illustrates the heat distribution to the payload and to the wire thermalization stages at 80 K and 5 K, respectively. The comparison of Cases 4, 5, and 6 suggests that the parasitic heat load to the payload can be reduced significantly if multiple wire thermalizations (at 80 K and 5 K) are present. Furthermore, the comparison between Case 2 and Case 5 enables an evaluation of the impact of different payload cooling concepts, as both cases follow the same thermal path (300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload). With the lower payload temperatures due to helium-based cooling, Case 5 results in a lower parasitic heat load than Case 2. This results from the fact that at low temperatures, electrical resistivity of copper decreases. The reduction in electrical resistivity lowers Joule heat, enabling smaller wire diameters to be selected via the optimization algorithm (cf. Section 4.1, and smaller diameters minimize the parasitic heat load.

Figure 5.2: Heat load distribution for different cases, divided among wire thermalization at 80 K, 5 K (if present) and the payload.

The same trend can be observed in the comparison between Cases 3 and 6. However, the parasitic heat load to the payload in Case 4 is slightly higher than in Case 1, despite the helium-based cooling concept in Case 4. This is due to the high temperature gradient in Case 4, as explained previously.

A key aspect of the evaluation is the reduction rate of parasitic heat load achieved through optimization. The reduction rate refers to how much the parasitic heat load decreases from the initial design (\dot{Q}_c Input) to the achievable design (\dot{Q}_c Achievable) after applying wire optimization and then adjusting diameters to commercially available sizes. Table 5.5 summarizes the parasitic heat load reduction rates for each case. The reduction rate ranges from a minimum of 7% to a maximum of 92%. Generally, the reduction rate of cases with helium-based cooling, cases 4, 5, and 6, is higher than those with monolithic cooling. This is due to fact that the electrical resistivity decreases at lower temperatures, which reduces Joule heat and this allows for the selection of smaller wire diameters. Furthermore, since parasitic heat load is directly proportional to the cross-section area of the wire, the reduction of wire diameter results in greater heat load reduction. In contrast, in monolithic cooling cases, where the payload temperatures are higher, electrical resistivity is higher, limiting how much the wire diameter can be reduced while still satisfying the limiting criterion (cf. Section 4.1). Moreover, in Case 6, the reduction of the parasitic heat load to the payload is only 7%. This results from the narrow temperature range (from 5 K to 2 K), where the thermal conductivity increases significantly.

In conclusion, Case 6 results in the lowest parasitic heat load to the payload, as expected, due to the combination of wire thermalization (at 80 K and 5 K) and helium-based payload cooling. In contrast, Case 4 results in the highest parasitic heat load to the payload, due to wide temperature gradient. The evaluation of the results confirm that wire thermalization at both 80 K and 5 K is highly effective in minimizing the parasitic heat load to the payload. However, it is important to note that this study compares different thermal analysis cases for the wires under the assumption that all electrical wires are made of copper (except the phosphor bronze Cernox wires). Given the strong dependence of thermal and electrical properties on material, further reductions in parasitic heat load could be achieved through material selection. A material study is therefore necessary to determine the full potential for reducing parasitic heat load in Case 6 by selecting alternative materials.

Table 5.5: The parasitic heat load reduction rates from \dot{Q}_c Input to \dot{Q}_c Achievable for each case

Case	\dot{Q}_c Input [W]	\dot{Q}_c Achievable [W]	Reduction Rate [%]
1 (to Payload)	2.95	1.78	40
2 (to Payload)	1.16	0.44	62
3 (to 5 K)	12.36	1.04	92
4 (to Payload)	3.07	1.78	42
5 (to Payload)	1.29	0.43	66
6 (to 5 K)	12.24	0.94	92
6 (to Payload)	0.027	0.026	7

5.4 Wire material selection

This section evaluates different materials for the electrical wires with the thermal configuration of Case 6 (see Table 5.2), in order to further reduce the parasitic heat load of the electrical wires. The selection of the appropriate materials for electrical wiring requires balancing electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity (see Chapter 2). Since no single material optimally satisfies both criteria, a systematic evaluation is necessary. The following subsection outlines the approach for material selection, then Subsection 5.4.2 compares different materials and determines the most suitable materials for the final electrical wiring design.

5.4.1 Material selection approach

Material properties, specifically electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity, directly influence the parasitic heat load at the cold end (see Section 2.2). To minimize this heat load, a material should ideally have both low electrical resistivity (to reduce Joule heat) and low thermal conductivity (to reduce the parasitic heat load at the cold end). However, no single material has both low electrical resistivity and low thermal conductivity simultaneously. For instance, as shown in Figures 5.3 and 5.4, between 300 K and 2 K, copper has the lowest electrical resistivity but also has the highest thermal conductivity among commonly used electrical wire materials. Therefore, the selection process must prioritize one property over the other depending on the operating conditions: current requirements and temperature ranges.

As discussed in Subsection 5.3, high-current wires contribute the most to the total parasitic heat load. Therefore, for high-current wires, materials with low electrical resistivity should be selected. In contrast, for low-current wires, Joule heat is negligibly low. Hence, materials with lower thermal conductivity can be more effective in reducing total parasitic heat load at the cold end. In addition to the current of the wire, the temperature range must also be considered in the selection process, since material properties are temperature-dependent. For instance, in Figure 5.4, copper exhibits a peak in thermal conductivity around 20 K. As a result, despite its low electrical resistivity, copper may no longer be the optimal choice in this temperature range, and an alternative material with lower thermal conductivity, such as phosphor bronze or manganin, could result in a lower parasitic heat load than copper.

By combining different currents and temperature ranges, a total of 14 material selection cases are established, as presented in Table 5.6. These cases arise from the classification of currents in Table 5.1 into three levels: low (below 10 mA), intermediate (100 mA), and high (1000 mA). In addition, four different temperature ranges are considered, based on the Case 6 of the thermal analysis cases (see Table 5.2). The material selection is applied to Case 6, as it resulted in the lowest parasitic heat load to the payload (see Subsection 5.3).

To determine the most suitable material for each case, seven different materials from Figures 5.3 and 5.4 are compared to copper. The optimization methodology described in Section 4.1 is applied to each material across the 14 material selection cases, while maintaining the wire lengths given in Table 5.1. This approach allows a direct comparison of which material performs best for a given current level and temperature range simultaneously.

Figure 5.3: Electrical resistivity of different materials as a function of temperature (Diagram plotted with material properties from [14])

Figure 5.4: Thermal conductivity of different materials as a function of temperature (Diagram plotted with material properties from [14])

Table 5.6: Overview of the 14 material selection cases with different current levels and thermal paths.

Case	Thermal Path	I_0 [mA]	L_0 [mm]	Case	Thermal Path	I_0 [mA]	L_0 [mm]
Wire thermalization at 80 K				Wire thermalization at 5 K			
1	300 K \rightarrow 80 K	1000	100	4	80 K \rightarrow 5 K	1000	100
2	300 K \rightarrow 80 K	100	100	5	80 K \rightarrow 5 K	100	100
3	300 K \rightarrow 80 K	10	100	6	80 K \rightarrow 5 K	10	100
Platform $T_{PF} = 2$ K				Marionette $T_{MA} = 2$ K			
7	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	1000	500	10	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	1000	1500
8	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	100	500	11	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	100	1500
9	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	10	500	12	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	10	1500
Test Mass $T_{TM} = 15$ K							
13	5 K \rightarrow 15 K	100	2700				
14	5 K \rightarrow 15 K	10	2700				

5.4.2 Wire material variation

Table 5.7 summarizes the two best-performing materials for each material selection case from 1 to 14. The first row in each case represents the best material, while the second row shows the next best alternative.

Between 300 K and 80 K (Cases 1–3), aluminum is the best material across all three current levels. For high and intermediate currents, copper follows as the second-best option, while for low currents, phosphor bronze performs better than copper. This aligns with expectations that, at lower currents, materials with lower thermal conductivity outperform copper in reducing overall parasitic heat load (see Subsection 5.4.1).

For the high-current wires between 80 K and 5 K (Case 4), aluminum no longer outperforms copper. This can be explained due to aluminum’s higher electrical resistivity compared to copper in this temperature range, which results in the need for larger diameters to carry the same current. At cryogenic temperatures, aluminum cannot achieve small diameters as copper, leading to higher heat loads. In contrast, for intermediate-current wires in the same temperature range (Case 5), aluminum results in a lower parasitic heat load than copper. For low-current wires (Case 6), Niobium-Titanium Alloy (NbTi) appears as an alternative after aluminum. However, since NbTi only becomes superconducting below 9 K, its benefits are not fully observed within this temperature range, allowing aluminum to remain as the best choice.

Although aluminum consistently ranks as the best material for cases with wire thermalization at 80 K and 5 K (Cases 1–6), it is generally not preferred for electrical wiring. Despite its low electrical resistivity, aluminum introduces several mechanical and practical challenges. First, aluminum is mechanically weaker (lower

Table 5.7: The two best-performing materials for each of the 14 material selection cases from Table 5.6, ranked from lowest to highest parasitic heat load (\dot{Q}_c).

Case	Material	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Case	Material	\dot{Q}_c [W]
1	Aluminum	0.04697	8	Copper	0.00008
	Copper	0.05043		Beryllium Copper	0.00010
2	Aluminum	0.00466	9	NbTi	$5.47 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	Copper	0.00705		Aluminum	$8.34 \cdot 10^{-6}$
3	Aluminum	0.00046	10	Aluminum	0.00083
	Phosphor Bronze	0.00075		Copper	0.00089
4	Copper	0.01192	11	Aluminum	0.00083
	Aluminum	0.03126		Copper	0.00083
5	Aluminum	0.00350	12	NbTi	$6.45 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	Copper	0.00507		Aluminum	$8.29 \cdot 10^{-6}$
6	Aluminum	0.00035	13	Copper	0.00025
	NbTi	0.00054		Aluminum	0.00025
7	Copper	0.00082	14	Copper	$2.53 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	Aluminum	0.00083		Aluminum	$2.54 \cdot 10^{-5}$

yield strength) than copper, making it less reliable under bending, vibration, or mechanical stress. Additionally, aluminum's high thermal expansion coefficient differs significantly from other commonly used materials in cryogenics, which can introduce mechanical stress and long-term reliability issues. Another critical aspect is aluminum's tendency to oxidize rapidly, forming a highly resistive oxide layer that interferes with electrical connections, particularly at joints. Furthermore, aluminum requires specialized ultrasonic bonding rather than conventional soldering. [1, 94] Given these limitations, aluminum will not be selected as electrical wire material despite its great thermal performance. Instead, in the cases, where aluminum ranks as number one, the second-best materials will be selected for the final design.

After comparing different materials for the electrical wires with the thermal paths $300 \text{ K} \rightarrow 80 \text{ K}$ and $80 \text{ K} \rightarrow 5 \text{ K}$ (Cases 1-6), the material selection proceeds for the wires that extend from 5 K to the payload components (Cases 7-14). A computational stiffness issue was encountered for high- and intermediate-current cases within the $5 \text{ K}-2 \text{ K}$ and $15 \text{ K}-5 \text{ K}$ range for the payload (Cases 7, 8, 10, 11 and 13). This computational stiffness likely arises either due to the material properties from [14] that introduce sharp discontinuities or extreme nonlinearity between 5 K and 2 K , or simply due to intrinsic numerical problems, making the differential equation (Eq. 2.11) numerically stiff and hard to solve with standard solving methods. Despite various attempts to resolve this issue through different numerical solving methods, no stable solution could be achieved. Given the time constraints, further investi-

gation was not feasible within the scope of this work. However, it is important to note that not all materials were affected by this issue, so for each remaining case, the successfully computed materials will be specified.

In Case 7, aluminum and copper was compared to each other, and copper outperformed aluminum. In Case 8, aluminum, copper, phosphor bronze and beryllium copper were evaluated, where copper remained as the best choice for the intermediate-current wires for the platform. In Case 9 (the low-current wires for the platform), the results for all materials were successfully computed and NbTi resulted in the lowest parasitic heat load. This is due to the fact that at this temperature range (from 5 K to 2 K), NbTi becomes superconducting, significantly reducing heat load.

For the high- and intermediate-current wires for the marionette (Case 10 and 11), only aluminum, copper and beryllium copper were evaluated due to the computational stiffness issues, as explained previously. Although aluminum resulted in a lower parasitic heat load, copper is selected for the high- and intermediate-current wires for the marionette, as aluminum is not a suitable material for electrical wires. In Case 12, for low-current wires for the marionette, NbTi is the best-performing material due to superconductivity.

Despite the superconductivity of NbTi, it cannot be used for actuation coils for the marionette, which are among the low-current electrical instruments (see Table 5.1). The electrical wires are connected to the actuation coils, therefore, selecting the wire material also determines the coil material. Since the coils apply force to the marionette with paired magnets through induced magnetic fields, the material's magnetic properties must be considered in addition to its electrical performance (cf. Section 3.1.1). Unlike copper, which has a stable relative permeability of 0.999 across all temperatures, NbTi has an unstable relative permeability, which only is close to zero under 9 K [95, 96]. Additionally, NbTi experiences superconducting flux pinning, a phenomenon where magnetic field lines become trapped and pinned within the material. This becomes problematic for actuation coils, as flux pinning interferes with the applied force. [97, 98] While there are solutions, such as multifilamentary NbTi with a copper matrix, this work does not consider the thermal behavior of such complex materials [34, 99]. Therefore, while NbTi remains a suitable option for other electrical instruments with low currents, it cannot be used for coils.

For the electrical wires for the test mass (Cases 13 and 14), it is important to note that no electrical instruments assigned to the test mass require high currents, simplifying the analysis to intermediate and low currents. Additionally, the test mass has a temperature of 15 K, which is higher than the temperature of the thermal shield (5 K) (see Section 5.2). While heat does not flow to the test mass, but rather from the test mass to 5 K, selecting a suitable material helps minimize the parasitic heat load to 5 K. For intermediate current wires for the test mass (Case 13), due to computational stiffness issues, the following materials were compared to each other: Copper, Manganin, Aluminum, Phosphor Bronze and Beryllium Copper. Copper resulted in the lowest parasitic heat load, with only a marginal difference compared to aluminum. Since aluminum is not a suitable material for the electrical wires, as explained previously, copper remains as the wire material for the intermediate-current wires for the test mass. Lastly, for low currents (Case 14), no material significantly outperforms copper, making it the most suitable choice.

In conclusion, based on these evaluations, the final selected material for each case is presented in Table 5.8. The results of the material variation confirm that priori-

tizing low electrical resistivity for high- and intermediate-current wires is the most effective strategy for minimizing parasitic heat load, even if the material has high thermal conductivity. In particular, copper is selected for high- and intermediate-currents across all temperature ranges (Cases 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11 and 13). In contrast, for low-current wires, where Joule heating is negligibly low, selecting materials with low thermal conductivity results in a minimal parasitic heat load, even if they exhibit higher electrical resistivity, for instance, phosphor bronze and NbTi (Cases 3, 6, 9 and 12). Exceptions were made in the material selection for Aluminum and NbTi. Aluminum is an unsuitable electrical wire material for various reasons: it forms a resistive oxide layer, is difficult to install due to soldering challenges, and is less reliable in long term operations due to its lower yield strength compared to copper [1, 94]. As a result, aluminum was not selected for any case. Furthermore, NbTi is not suitable specifically for the actuation coil wires extending to the marionette and test mass. Although NbTi is superconducting, it also experiences flux pinning and has a different relative permeability than copper, which can interfere with the applied force to the payload components [96, 97]. This exception for the actuation coil wires is denoted with * in Case 12 in Table 5.8. This material selection approach ensured that the parasitic heat load is minimized for each case based on the specific operational conditions (current level and temperature range).

Overall, with the material selection, the total heat load on 80 K and 5 K is reduced by 19% and 42% respectively, in comparison to the minimum achievable parasitic heat load results of Case 6. However, no significant change of the parasitic heat load to the payload is observed. This is due to the fact that only the material of the wires with low currents in the payload could be changed from copper to different alternatives, which did not significantly impact the total parasitic heat load to the payload. This concludes the material selection, and the next section will introduce the final electrical wiring design for the ET-LF payload.

Table 5.8: Overview of the selected materials for each case from Table 5.6. Case 12 denotes the exception for coil wires with *.

Case	Material	Case	Material
1	Copper	8	Copper
2	Copper	9	NbTi
3	Phosphor Bronze	10	Copper
4	Copper	11	Copper
5	Copper	12	*NbTi
6	NbTi	13	Copper
7	Copper	14	Copper

5.5 Design Proposal

The design proposal for the electrical wiring of the ET-LF payload is presented in this section. In total, there are 170 electrical wires for the electrical instruments located on the payload components. The goal was to minimize the total parasitic heat load from the electrical wires to the payload. This design is based on the

evaluation of different payload cooling concepts, wire thermalization strategies and wire material selections, by assessing their impact on parasitic heat load reduction discussed in the previous sections.

Through the wire optimization methodology (see Section 4.1), the parasitic heat load of the electrical wires was successfully minimized, achieving reductions of up to 92% compared to the initial configurations. Furthermore, material selection provided an additional improvement, reducing the parasitic heat load to 80 K by 19% and to 5 K by 42% compared to the minimum achievable parasitic heat load in Case 6 (s. Section 5.4.2). The worst performing case (Case 4) resulted in a total parasitic heat load of 1.78 W to the payload. In contrast, the best performing case (Case 6) the parasitic heat load to the payload was only 0.03 W. (s. Section 5.3) A material selection study was conducted for Case 6. For low-current wires, materials with lower thermal conductivity in comparison to copper resulted in lower parasitic heat loads. For high- and intermediate-current wires, copper remained as the most suitable material, as the electrical resistivity of copper is the lowest among considered materials. In addition to the final selected materials presented in Table 5.8, an exception was made for the low-current wires in the test mass. While Copper was initially selected for low-current wires, the final design evaluation showed that beryllium copper resulted in a lower parasitic heat load for the Cernox wires, as they carry the lowest current among all wires. It is important to note that in the calculations for different materials, computational stiffness issues arose, specifically for the wires with high- and intermediate current, between the temperatures 5 K and 2 K. However, this issue only affected 2% of the calculations in the entirety of this thesis. Despite this, the best possible material choices were made based on the available results for the affected calculations. In conclusion, with the final design, the total parasitic heat load to the payload is 0.026, as presented in Table 5.9. The details such as wire diameters and lengths along with the selected material for each wire is provided in Tables 5.12, 5.11 and 5.12.

Table 5.9: Overview of the total parasitic heat load values of the proposed electrical wiring design

Section	Thermal Path	\dot{Q}_c [W]
Wire thermalization at 80 K:	300 K \rightarrow 80 K	1.88789
Wire thermalization at 5 K:	80 K \rightarrow 5 K	0.54078
To Platform $T_{PF} = 2$ K:	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	0.01476
To Marionette $T_{MA} = 2$ K:	5 K \rightarrow 2 K	0.01086
From Test Mass $T_{TM} = 15$ K:	15 K \rightarrow 5 K	0.01088
Total to 80 K		1.88789
Total to 5 K		0.55166
Total to Payload		0.02561

Table 5.10: Design proposal for electrical wiring between 300 K and 80 K.

Input	Instrument Type	Material	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_0 [mm]	L_0 [mm]
For Platform							
1	Piezo Actuator	Copper	6	100	38	0.1007	110
2	*LVDT	Copper	12	100	38	0.1007	110
3	Stepper Motor	Copper	16	1000	30	0.2546	110
4	Cernox	Phosphor Bronze	4	0.01	36	0.1270	110
For Marionette							
5	Photodiode	Phosphor Bronze	24	10	36	0.1270	110
6	LED	Copper	12	350	35	0.1426	100
7	Stepper Motor	Copper	8	1000	30	0.2546	110
8	Coil	Phosphor Bronze	12	9.4	36	0.1270	110
9	Cernox	Phosphor Bronze	8	0.01	36	0.1270	110
For Test Mass							
10	Photodiode	Phosphor Bronze	24	10	36	0.1270	110
11	LED	Copper	12	350	35	0.1426	100
12	Coil	Phosphor Bronze	8	1.7	36	0.1270	110
13	*Picomotor TM	Phosphor Bronze	8	10	36	0.1270	110
14	*Picomotor CP	Phosphor Bronze	8	10	36	0.1270	110
15	Cernox	Phosphor Bronze	8	0.01	36	0.1270	110

Table 5.11: Design proposal for electrical wiring between 80 K and 5 K.

Input	Instrument Type	Material	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_0 [mm]	L_0 [mm]
For Platform							
1	Piezo Actuator	Copper	6	100	38	0.1007	110
2	*LVDT	Copper	12	100	38	0.1007	110
3	Stepper Motor	Copper	16	1000	35	0.1426	100
4	Cernox	NbTi	4	0.01	38	0.1007	110
For Marionette							
5	Photodiode	NbTi	24	10	22	0.6438	110
6	LED	Copper	12	350	38	0.1007	110
7	Stepper Motor	Copper	8	1000	35	0.1426	100
8	Coil	NbTi	12	9.4	27	0.3606	110
9	Cernox	NbTi	8	0.01	38	0.1007	110
For Test Mass							
10	Photodiode	NbTi	24	10	22	0.6438	110
11	LED	Copper	12	350	38	0.1007	110
12	Coil	NbTi	8	1.7	30	0.2546	110
13	*Picomotor TM	NbTi	8	10	22	0.6438	110
14	*Picomotor CP	NbTi	8	10	22	0.6438	110
15	Cernox	NbTi	8	0.01	38	0.1007	110

Table 5.12: Design proposal for electrical wiring between 5 K and payload

Input	Instrument Type	Material	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_0 [mm]	L_0 [mm]
Platform $T_{PF} = 2$ K							
1	Piezo Actuator	Copper	6	100	31	0.2268	530
2	*LVDT	Copper	12	100	31	0.2268	530
3	Stepper Motor	Copper	16	1000	21	0.7229	540
4	Cernox	NbTi	4	0.01	37	0.1131	570
Marionette $T_{MA} = 2$ K							
5	Photodiode	NbTi	24	10	4	5.1894	1790
6	LED	Copper	12	350	21	0.7229	1540
7	Stepper Motor	Copper	8	1000	15	1.4495	1900
8	Coil	Copper	12	9.4	36	0.1270	1770
9	Cernox	NbTi	8	0.01	34	0.1601	1650
Test Mass $T_{TM} = 15$ K							
10	Photodiode	Copper	24	10	38	0.1007	3190
11	LED	Copper	12	350	23	0.5733	2950
12	Coil	Copper	8	1.7	38	0.1007	3400
13	*Picomotor TM	Copper	8	10	38	0.1007	3190
14	*Picomotor CP	Copper	8	10	38	0.1007	3190
15	Cernox	Beryllium Copper	8	0.01	45	0.0447	3400

6. Summary and Outlook

The Einstein Telescope is still in the design stage, making any research dedicated to it particularly significant. An important yet often overlooked component in gravitational wave detectors is the electrical wiring of the payload. The electrical wires power various instruments inside the payload, ensuring the stability and efficient performance of the detector. In cryogenic payloads, the design and consideration of electrical wires are crucial due to their parasitic heat contribution. The minimization of the parasitic heat load is necessary, as it uses the available cooling power at the cold end of the system. The primary goal of this thesis was to establish a methodology for optimizing the electrical wires, aiming to minimize their parasitic heat load. Another key objective was to propose a design for the electrical wires of the Einstein Telescope's low frequency cryogenic payload.

To achieve this, the theoretical foundations of the thermal behavior of electrical wires were first studied. This was followed by a study of gravitational wave detectors, starting with fundamental concepts of gravitational wave detectors. To propose a design for the electrical wires for the Einstein Telescope's low frequency cryogenic payload, two existing detectors, Advance Virgo and KAGRA, were thoroughly studied, to identify the used electrical instruments in the payload. Based on these studies, the electrical instruments to be used in the Einstein Telescope's low frequency cryogenic payload were selected. Afterwards, the wire optimization methodology was developed: The diameter of the wires were reduced iteratively until a limiting criterion was met, where the heat load on the warm end of the wire must not be smaller than the generated Joule heat. This criterion ensured that the wire can safely carry the required current, without overheating, and resulting in a minimum parasitic heat load at their cold end. After the determination of the wire diameter, the wire length was increased iteratively, based on the limiting criterion. This methodology for wire optimization was applied to the electrical wires of the GRAVITHELIUM Test Cryostat [90], a test facility to investigate the mechanical dissipation in cryogenic payload suspensions for the Einstein Telescope's low frequency cryogenic payload.

Afterwards, the wire optimization methodology was used to design the electrical wires for the Einstein Telescope's low frequency cryogenic payload. In order to analyze the impact of different cooling concepts for the payload and thermalization of the wires, six different thermal analysis cases for the electrical wires based on two

different cooling concepts (monolithic and helium-based cooling) were established. These cases were analyzed individually with the application of the developed wire optimization methodology.

The optimization of the electrical wires reduced the parasitic heat load with reduction rates up to 92% in the thermal analysis cases. The results suggested that wire thermalization before extending into the payload is necessary for minimizing parasitic heat load in both cooling concepts. Furthermore, the results showed that the wires assigned to the platform, contribute the most to the parasitic heat load, in comparison to the ones connected to the marionette or test mass, as these wires are connected to multiple instruments which need high currents. The worst performing Case (Case 4) was where helium-based cooling of the payload was used and no wire thermalization was present. This case resulted in a 1.8 W parasitic heat load to the payload. In contrast, Case 6 with helium cooling and wire thermalization at 80 K and 5 K, respectively, was the best performing case with 0.03 W parasitic heat load to the payload.

To further reduce the parasitic heat load, a material study was conducted based on the Case 6. Seven different materials were tested, and their thermal performance was compared to copper. The study concluded that materials with low thermal conductivity are more suitable than the ones with lower electrical resistivity, for low-current wires. In contrast, copper remained as the best choice for high-current wires, even at cryogenic temperatures. The study also highlighted that for coil wires inside the payload, material selection should not only consider thermal behavior but also the magnetic properties, to ensure stable actuation. The proposed design for the electrical wiring of the Einstein Telescope's low frequency payload consists of 170 wires. In the final design, the total heat load to the payload was calculated as 0.03 W.

While the wire optimization methodology proved highly effective, certain materials exhibited computational stiffness issues, particularly between 5 K and 2 K, for the wires with high- and intermediate-currents. However, these represented only 2% of the total calculations, and material selection was successfully completed for all remaining cases, with the affected cases still optimized using the most suitable available materials.

In conclusion, this thesis provides a first optimized design for the electrical wires in the low-frequency cryogenic payload of the Einstein Telescope, resulting from an optimization methodology developed for the electrical wires in cryogenics. The proposed design is a step forward in designing electrical wires with minimum parasitic heat load. Future research could further investigate material selection with complex materials, such as embedded matrix structures, which may offer improved thermal and electrical performance over pure materials. Additionally, while this study focused on thermal optimization, electromagnetic interference between the wires and the effects of wire twisting on mechanical and electrical behavior remain as open research topics. The investigation of these aspects could refine the optimization of the electrical wire design in the low frequency cryogenic payload of the Einstein Telescope.

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A. Appendix

Purpose of Use	AdV+			KAGRA			
	Platform (Filter 7)	Marionette	Test Mass	Platform	Marionette	Intermediate Mass	Test Mass
Displacement							
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 LVDTs • 3 position sensors (piezos with a set of 3 coils) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 252 photodiodes • With printed circuit board, microcontroller, and analog to digital converter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 reflective photo sensors (each sensor has 2 photodiodes and 1 LED) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 reflective photo sensors (each sensor has 2 photodiodes and 1 LED) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -
Position							
Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 coils • 4 stepper motors • 1 motor for the fishing rod 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 coils • 2 stepper motors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 coils (mirror) • 2 picomotors (CP) • 2 picomotors (RH) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving mass system (with stepper motor) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving mass system (with stepper motor) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 coils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 coils
Thermal and Optical Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ring heater (RH) (with 2 NiCr coils for heating, 2 PT100s) • Compensation plate (CP) • Instrumented baffle (with HWS and photodiodes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cernox temperature sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cernox temperature sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cernox temperature sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cernox temperature sensor • Baffle

Table A.1: Comparison of instruments of payloads of AdV+ and KAGRA, categorized depending on their location (platform, marionette, intermediate mass, test mass) and purpose of use (displacement measurement, position adjustment, thermal compensation). Instruments that either do not exist or could not be identified using publicly available information are denoted with —.

Table A.2: Optimized heat load results for Case 1: 300 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{PF} = 13$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	35	0.1426	560	0.005070	0.030420	0.899448
2	*LVDI	12	100	35	0.1426	560	0.005070	0.060840	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	25	0.4547	570	0.050511	0.808179	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	56	0.0125	610	0.000002	0.000010	
Marionette $T_{PF} = 17$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	40	0.0799	1720	0.000505	0.012126	0.635474
6	LED	12	350	25	0.4547	1590	0.017707	0.212484	
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	20	0.8118	1780	0.050645	0.405163	
8	Coil	12	9.4	40	0.0799	1830	0.000474	0.005685	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	52	0.0199	1850	0.000002	0.000016	
Test Mass $T_{PF} = 20$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	37	0.1131	3370	0.000506	0.012139	
11	LED	12	350	22	0.6438	3110	0.017748	0.212970	0.233887
12	Coil	8	1.7	45	0.0447	3100	0.000086	0.000686	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	36	0.1131	3370	0.000506	0.004046	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	36	0.1131	3370	0.000506	0.004046	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	52	0.0251	3340	0.000002	0.000014	
Total Payload									1.768809

Table A.3: Optimized heat load results for Case 2: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{\text{PF}} = 13$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	36	0.1131	590	0.001223	0.007339	0.217869
2	*LVDT	12	100	36	0.1131	590	0.001223	0.014679	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	27	0.3606	600	0.012241	0.195850	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	56	0.0125	610	0.000000	0.000001	
Marionette $T_{\text{PF}} = 17$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	42	0.0633	1750	0.000123	0.002963	
6	LED	12	350	27	0.3606	1620	0.004326	0.051906	0.155006
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	22	0.6438	1810	0.012343	0.098742	
8	Coil	12	9.4	42	0.0633	1860	0.000116	0.001393	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	52	0.0199	1850	0.000000	0.000002	
Test Mass $T_{\text{PF}} = 20$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	39	0.0897	3300	0.000124	0.002987	
11	LED	12	350	24	0.5106	3000	0.004422	0.053064	0.058214
12	Coil	8	1.7	47	0.0355	3000	0.000021	0.000171	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	39	0.0897	3300	0.000124	0.000996	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	39	0.0897	3300	0.000124	0.000996	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	50	0.0251	3340	0.000000	0.000002	
Total Payload									0.431089

Table A.4: Optimized heat load results for Case 3: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload with monolithic cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{PF} = 13$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	34	0.1601	550	0.000245	0.001470	0.043595
2	*LVDI	12	100	34	0.1601	550	0.000245	0.002941	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	24	0.5106	560	0.002449	0.039183	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	49	0.0281	610	0.000000	0.000000	
Marionette $T_{PF} = 17$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	39	0.0799	1590	0.000036	0.000871	0.045747
6	LED	12	350	24	0.5106	1790	0.001305	0.015654	
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	20	0.8118	1660	0.003602	0.028817	
8	Coil	12	9.4	40	0.0799	1720	0.000034	0.000405	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	46	0.0398	1500	0.000000	0.000000	
Test Mass $T_{PF} = 20$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	38	0.1007	2910	0.000044	0.001045	
11	LED	12	350	22	0.6438	3400	0.001523	0.018282	0.020083
12	Coil	8	1.7	45	0.0447	3400	0.000007	0.000059	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	38	0.1007	2910	0.000044	0.000348	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	38	0.1007	2910	0.000044	0.000348	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	44	0.0502	2860	0.000000	0.000000	
Total Payload									0.109425

Table A.5: Optimized heat load results for Case 4: 300 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{PF} = 2$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	35	0.1426	590	0.005026	0.030157	0.902665
2	*IVDT	12	100	35	0.1426	590	0.005026	0.060314	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	25	0.4547	590	0.050761	0.812176	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	56	0.0158	520	0.000004	0.000018	
Marionette $T_{MA} = 2$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	40	0.0799	1830	0.000504	0.012101	
6	LED	12	350	25	0.4547	1690	0.017689	0.212266	0.633957
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	20	0.8118	1890	0.050482	0.403854	
8	Coil	12	9.4	41	0.0711	1540	0.000475	0.005703	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	49	0.0281	1800	0.000004	0.000033	
Test Mass $T_{TM} = 15$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	38	0.1007	2760	0.000506	0.012144	
11	LED	12	350	22	0.6438	3240	0.017681	0.212168	0.233114
12	Coil	8	1.7	45	0.0447	3220	0.000086	0.000688	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	38	0.1007	2760	0.000506	0.004048	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	38	0.1007	2760	0.000506	0.004048	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	50	0.0251	2700	0.000002	0.000017	
Total Payload									1.769736

Table A.6: Optimized heat load results for Case 5: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{\text{PF}} = 2$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	38	0.1007	500	0.001233	0.007400	0.635474
2	*LVDI	12	100	38	0.1007	500	0.001233	0.014801	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	28	0.3211	510	0.012296	0.196736	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	49	0.0158	520	0.000000	0.000002	
Marionette $T_{\text{MA}} = 2$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	43	0.0564	1590	0.000122	0.002933	0.233887
6	LED	12	350	27	0.3606	1860	0.004270	0.051238	
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	23	0.5733	1640	0.012229	0.097829	
8	Coil	12	9.4	43	0.0564	1690	0.000115	0.001378	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	49	0.0281	1800	0.000000	0.000003	
Test Mass $T_{\text{TM}} = 15$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	40	0.0799	2890	0.000122	0.002936	
11	LED	12	350	24	0.5106	3380	0.004280	0.051363	0.057307
12	Coil	8	1.7	46	0.0355	3350	0.000021	0.000167	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	40	0.0799	2890	0.000122	0.000979	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	40	0.0799	2890	0.000122	0.000979	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	50	0.0251	2710	0.000000	0.000002	
Total Payload									0.926668

Table A.7: Optimized heat load results for Case 6: 300 K \rightarrow 80 K \rightarrow 5 K \rightarrow Payload with helium cooling

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform $T_{PF} = 2$ K									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	31	0.2268	530	0.000083	0.000498	0.014757
2	*LVDT	12	100	31	0.2268	530	0.000083	0.000996	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	21	0.7229	540	0.000829	0.013263	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	50	0.0502	500	0.000000	0.000000	
Marionette $T_{MA} = 2$ K									
5	Photodiode	24	10	36	0.1270	1660	0.000008	0.000199	
6	LED	12	350	21	0.7229	1540	0.000290	0.003480	0.010899
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	17	1.4500	1900	0.000891	0.007127	
8	Coil	12	9.4	36	0.1270	1770	0.000008	0.000093	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	39	0.0799	1500	0.000000	0.000000	
Test Mass $T_{TM} = 15$ K									
10	Photodiode	24	10	38	0.1007	3190	0.000025	0.000607	
11	LED	12	350	23	0.5733	2950	0.000886	0.010636	0.011683
12	Coil	8	1.7	47	0.0398	2930	0.000004	0.000034	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	38	0.1007	3190	0.000025	0.000202	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	38	0.1007	3190	0.000025	0.000202	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	50	0.0502	2860	0.000000	0.000000	
Total Payload									0.025657

Table A.8: Optimized heat load results for the intermediate thermalization stage at 80 K

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	40	0.0799	110	0.004995	0.029971	0.896833
2	*LVDT	12	100	40	0.0799	110	0.004995	0.059942	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	30	0.2546	110	0.050432	0.806917	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	73	0.0028	100	0.000000	0.000003	
Marionette									
5	Photodiode	24	10	50	0.0250	110	0.000494	0.011864	0.631103
6	LED	12	350	35	0.1426	100	0.017499	0.209984	
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	30	0.2546	110	0.050432	0.403458	
8	Coil	12	9.4	50	0.0250	110	0.000483	0.005791	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	73	0.0028	100	0.000000	0.000006	
Test Mass									
10	Photodiode	24	10	50	0.0250	110	0.000494	0.011864	
11	LED	12	350	35	0.1426	100	0.017499	0.209984	0.230440
12	Coil	8	1.7	47	0.0099	100	0.000085	0.000678	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	50	0.0250	110	0.000494	0.003955	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	50	0.0250	110	0.000494	0.003955	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	73	0.0028	100	0.000000	0.000006	
Total 80 K									1.758376

Table A.9: Optimized heat load results for the intermediate thermalization stage at 5 K

Input	Instrument Type	Total Wire	I_0 [mA]	AWG	d_{\min} [mm]	L_{\max} [mm]	\dot{Q}_c [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c from all wires of the input [W]	Total \dot{Q}_c per section [W]
Platform									
1	Piezo Actuator	6	100	45	0.0447	100	0.001181	0.007086	0.211940
2	*LVDT	12	100	45	0.0447	100	0.001181	0.014172	
3	Stepper Motor	16	1000	35	0.1426	100	0.011917	0.190666	
4	Cernox	4	0.01	52	0.0223	110	0.000004	0.000017	
Marionette									
5	Photodiode	24	10	55	0.0140	100	0.000117	0.002799	0.150740
6	LED	12	350	39	0.0897	110	0.004266	0.051194	
7	Stepper Motor	8	1000	35	0.1426	100	0.011917	0.095333	
8	Coil	12	9.4	55	0.0140	100	0.000115	0.001380	
9	Cernox	8	0.01	52	0.0223	110	0.000004	0.000034	
Test Mass									
10	Photodiode	24	10	55	0.0140	100	0.000117	0.002799	
11	LED	12	350	39	0.0897	110	0.004266	0.051194	0.056058
12	Coil	8	1.7	47	0.0062	110	0.000021	0.000165	
13	*Picomotor TM	8	10	55	0.0140	100	0.000117	0.000933	
14	*Picomotor CP	8	10	55	0.0140	100	0.000117	0.000933	
15	Cernox	8	0.01	52	0.0223	110	0.000004	0.000034	
Total 5 K									0.418738